

Developmental sculpting of neuronal network and function in the cerebellum

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DECLARATION

This thesis is a presentation of my original research work. Wherever contributions of others are involved, every effort is made to indicate this clearly, with due reference to the literature, and acknowledgement of collaborative research and discussions.

The work was done under the guidance of Prof. Vatsala Thirumalai, at the National Centre for Biological Sciences, Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Bangalore.

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In my capacity as supervisor of the candidate's thesis, I certify that the above statements are true to the best of my knowledge.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 The Cerebellar circuit

The cerebellum is an evolutionarily conserved brain region required for motor control, coordination and balance (**Fig. 1.1**). It has a layered structure with a dorsal neuropil-dense region called the molecular layer, a middle Purkinje neuron (PN) layer and a ventrally located granule cell layer (**Fig. 1.2 A**). Together, these layers make up the cerebellar cortex. PNs are the principal neurons of the cerebellar cortex. They receive two major excitatory inputs from: the parallel fiber (PF) axons of the granule cells and the climbing fiber (CF) axons of the inferior olivary neurons. The PNs receive inputs from the PFs and CFs via their elaborate dendritic arbour. Third type of afferents carrying aminergic inputs to the cerebellum form direct contacts with PNs in mammals. PNs also receive local Inhibitory inputs from the cerebellar interneurons and other PNs ([reviewed by Ito 2009](#)). PN-PN connectivity, however, has not been reported in other species like teleosts ([Sitaraman et al 2021](#)). PNs perform complex computations and send inhibitory instructions to the eurydendroid cells (in teleosts) or the deep cerebellar nuclei (DCN, in mammals). Both DCN and eurydendroid cells relay the signals to brain regions upstream and downstream of the cerebellum (Ikenaga et al., 2005, 2006). The excitatory synapses to the PNs are glutamatergic- with both NMDA and AMPA receptors at the PF-PN synapses and adult CF-PN synapses. However, functional NMDA receptors are absent at the CF-PN synapses during early postnatal development (Piochon et al., 2007; Sitaraman et al., 2021).

The PNs are inhibitory neurons of the cerebellum known for their characteristic elaborate dendritic arbour. The proximal dendrites are innervated by the CFs, whereas, the distal part of the arbour is innervated by the PFs (**Fig. 1.2 A**, [Hámori & Szentágothai, 1966](#), [Ichikawa et al 2015](#)). A fraction of the PN population is also known to have more than one primary dendrite ([Busch & Hansel, 2023](#)). The parallel fibre inputs are largely sensory, whereas the CF inputs are both sensory and motor in nature (Knogler et al., 2019; Narayanan et al., 2024; Félix et al., 2024). This makes the PNs a good site for

sensory-motor integration. To perform this integration efficiently, the circuit is designed to contain PNs that are mono-innervated by CFs and poly-innervated by PFs. As a result, many weak PF inputs and a single strong CF converge on each PN. The PF inputs are extensively shared between the PNs, whereas the CF inputs are more specific and are shared only between a few PNs (Woodward et al., 1974; Crepel et al., 1976). This design is achieved via postnatal developmental pruning (Kano et al., 2018). This precise organization of the cerebellar circuit during early development underpins its role in sensory-motor integration and coordinating complex behaviours.

1.2 Cerebellar development and metamorphosis

The cerebellum's characteristic, well-studied laminar organisation and conserved architecture make it an ideal microcircuit for studying circuit formation mechanisms. The presence of transient elements in cerebellar development has prompted its comparison to metamorphosis (van Welie et al., 2011). These elements include transient excitatory GABA currents (Brickley et al., 1996; Eilers et al., 2001), prolonged neurogenesis of granule cells in a transient layer, transient electrical synapses (Van Der Giessen et al., 2006), transient monosynaptic GABAergic connections between PNs (Watt et al., 2009), and the transient poly-innervation of PNs by CFs (Kano et al., 2018).

Furthermore, the abundance of fast AMPA currents and slow NMDA currents also changes (Piochon et al., 2007; Ripellino et al., 1997). Postsynaptic expression of NMDA receptors in PNs declines between the first and second postnatal weeks, only to rise again by the third week. During this rising phase, an NBQX-resistant and APV-sensitive NMDA component emerges in CF EPSCs (Piochon et al., 2007). This temporal patterning of NMDA receptors potentially allows for LTD/ LTP at the PF-PN synapses that are co-active with CF-PN synapses.

CF inputs carry teaching/ error signals that drive PN activity and thereby facilitate cerebellar learning and plasticity (Albus, 1971; Eccles et al., 1966; Ito & Kano, 1982; Marr, 1969; Suvrathan et al., 2016). At the time of birth, PNs are innervated by multiple perisomatic CFs. During early postnatal development, the excess fibres are pruned in an activity-dependent manner, giving rise to a winner fibre that translocates to the dendrites and strengthens its contact with the PN (Mikuni et al., 2013). Consequently, mono-innervated PN populations emerge over development (Kano et al., 2018). CF pruning is a crucial event in the development of cerebellar microcircuit as the CF inputs regulate synaptic plasticity at PF-PC levels.

Therefore, the transience of cerebellar development involves three important processes: synaptic refinement, neurogenesis and synaptogenesis. These processes occur parallelly to give rise to a mature cerebellum. While the molecular orchestration of these processes is abundantly studied, their functional relevance remains to be explored. In this thesis, I will use larval zebrafish as a model system to address (a) functional implications of synaptic

refinement of CF-PN synapses (Chapter 2), (b) evaluate PN neurogenesis and functional integration of new-born PNs in the cerebellar circuit (Chapter 3) and, (c) briefly touch upon PN activity patterns and the role of gap junctions in the maturation of cerebellar circuit (Chapter 4).

1.3 Larval zebrafish as a model system to study development and function of cerebellum

So far, it has been challenging to study motor behaviours in developing mammals due to their late emergence and limited accessibility to the cerebellum. The zebrafish cerebellum begins to form at roughly 2 days post fertilisation (dpf), which is just around the time when larvae hatch out of the chorionic membrane. Furthermore, if the experiment requires, the embryos can even be dechorionated safely as early as 24 hours post fertilisation (hpf), using mechanical or chemical treatments (Hasegawa et al., 2023). Zebrafish larvae are small, transparent and genetically tractable which makes them suitable for asking a multitude of interesting questions about the development and function of the cerebellum. Their overall small size further makes them amenable to simultaneous monitoring of behaviour and neurophysiology. Imaging and electrophysiology experiments have shown that the cerebellum is active during natural sensory-motor behaviours even during these early larval stages (Ahrens et al., 2012; Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015; Knogler et al., 2019; Hsieh et al., 2014). Therefore, in this study, I will utilise zebrafish to investigate the development and function of evolutionarily conserved cerebellum, often referred to as the 'little brain'.

1.4 Zebrafish cerebellar development

The zebrafish cerebellum undergoes constant expansion and organisation, especially during the first two weeks of development. Using parvalbumin immunostaining, Hamling et al., 2015 have created a spatiotemporal map of the growing PN population. While the depth and lateral width of the PN layer remain constant, The anterior-posterior length almost doubles during this period. Consequently, a logarithmic increase in PN layer

volume is observed. Growth of the PN population is also seen during this phase using BrdU pulse experiments. In addition to population growth, individual PNs also undergo rapid remodelling of morphology. Initially, immature PNs extend multiple dendritic neurites. A Golgi body apparatus is then localised at a specific position in the soma that serves as the site for future primary dendrite. This localisation is mediated by the atypical protein kinase C (aPKC) that autonomously regulates the primary dendrite specification. The importance of aPKC can be further evidenced in the aPKC mutants where golgi localisation is disrupted and the PNs continue to retain stellate appearance (Tanabe et al., 2010). Once the polarity is established, the primary dendrite undergoes an enhanced arborisation. Gap junction coupling and local translation facilitate dendritic branching and growth towards the dorsal neuropil region (Hamling et al., 2015; Sitaraman et al., 2021). While the PN layer is undergoing growth and maturation, PNs undergo innervation by CFs as early as 3 dpf. The granule cells also appear roughly at 2-3 dpf and innervate the distal dendrites through their parallel fibre axons (Takeuchi et al., 2015).

1.5 Zebrafish PNs

In zebrafish, PNs largely project locally to the Eurydendroid cells within the cerebellum (**Fig. 1.2 A**). A subset of the neurons also project distally to the hindbrain (Knogler et al., 2019). PNs show characteristic expression of markers like aldolase C (*Aldoc*, a glycolytic enzyme also known as zebrin II), parvalbumin7 and carbonic anhydrase (Bae et al., 2009; Matsui et al., 2014; Namikawa et al., 2019; Sitaraman et al., 2021). Aldoca or zebrin II promoter has been extensively used for specific labelling of PNs. However, this expression system also labels the zebrafish forebrain habenular neurons that project to the median raphe located ventral to the cerebellum. In zebrafish, a 258 bp enhancer element upstream to the *carbonic anhydrase VIII (ca8)* gene allows PN-specific expression (**Fig. 1.2 B**, (Matsui et al., 2014; Namikawa et al., 2019)). When Ca8 enhancer is fused with cFos minimal promoter or E1b minimal promoter, it further makes the expression specific to PNs (**Fig. 1.2 B, C**, (Namikawa et al., 2019; Sitaraman et al., 2021)).

Zebrafish PNs are electrically active with functional CF inputs by 4 dpf (Hsieh et al., 2014; Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015). Like mammals, zebrafish PNs are known for their characteristic spontaneous tonic firing of simple spikes (Hsieh et al., 2014; Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015). These spikes are intrinsic to PNs and are present even when the

neuron is isolated from the network using synaptic blockers. However, they disappear when sodium channels are blocked by bath application of tetrodotoxin (extracellular sodium channel blocker) as well as intracellular application of QX-314 (intracellular sodium channel blocker). This observation led to the finding that simple spikes are driven by sodium channels. Like mammals, tonic firing in zebrafish PNs is sustained by coupling of high voltage-gated calcium to calcium-dependent potassium channels. However, the channel types differ. Mammalian PNs use P/Q-type calcium channels while zebrafish PNs use L-type calcium channels. In larval zebrafish, tonic firing is sustained via calcium influx from L-type voltage-gated calcium channels that activate the SK channels and thereby allow repolarisation and hyperpolarisation and facilitate sodium channel availability (Chapter 4, ([Jadhav et al., 2024](#))).

In tonic state, the PNs usually rest around -45 mV. In addition to tonic spiking, PNs also exist in a bursting state when resting at a hyperpolarized membrane potential of ~-65mV. The bursting state is largely driven by synaptic inputs. Isolating the PNs from the network prevents them from bursting. Both inhibitory and excitatory inputs contribute to the bursting state. From the findings by Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015, we know that GABAA receptors, when blocked, alter the shape of bursts and blocking of AMPA receptors completely abolishes the bursts. Burst starts are also coincident with an increased frequency of CF inputs. This explains the role of AMPA receptors, which are present in abundance at the CF-PN synapses.

Zebrafish PNs are capable of switching between tonic and bursting states spontaneously or upon injection of a depolarizing or hyperpolarizing current pulse. This makes them bistable. Although a subject of debate, a similar, but not identical, activity pattern is also seen in the mammalian systems. A hyperpolarized quiescent stage and a depolarized spiking state are seen in PNs of rats, and guinea pigs ([Loewenstein et al., 2005](#)).

Figure 1.2 Introduction to zebrafish cerebellum and PNs

A. Schematic of larval zebrafish cerebellar circuit.

B. Left: DNA sequence to drive PN-specific expression of GFP using *carbonic anhydrase VIII* (Ca8) enhancer fused with E1b minimal promoter. The fusion sequence is referred to as *cpce* or Ca8 promoter-derived PC-specific enhancer element. Right: Expression of GFP in Tg(*cpce*-E1b:GFP) in a 4 dpf larva. Scale bar 1 mm (reproduced from Namikawa et al., 2019).

C. Co-localization of GFP (driven by *cpce*) and parvalbumin (PN marker) supports the specificity of *cpce* driven expression in PNs. Scale bars 50 μ m (for whole cerebellum images) and 10 μ m (for magnified images of PNs) (reproduced from Namikawa et al., 2019).

In addition to *cpce* (Ca8-E1b), Ca8-*cfos* also drives PN-specific expression in larval zebrafish (Sitaraman et al, 2021)

1.6 The inferior olivary neurons and CFs

The inferior olivary (IO) nucleus is located in the ventral hindbrain and sends contralateral axonal projections (called the climbing fibres or CFs) to the cerebellum. The fibres crossover at the level of the nucleus and then gradually ascend dorsally as they reach the cerebellum and innervate the PNs (**Fig. 1.3 A, B**). The IO neurons can be visualised and genetically accessed in Gal4 enhancer trap lines like Tg(hspGFFDMC28C-Gal4) (Takeuchi et al., 2015) and Tg(y320-Gal4) (Marquart et al., 2015) (**Fig. 1.3 A**). CF inputs serve as a training or error signal for motor planning and coordination in the PNs (Kimpo et al., 2014; Narayanan et al., 2024; Pi et al., 2024). CF inputs are also important for vestibulo ocular reflex (VOR) as their inhibition blocks plasticity of the VOR, suggesting their sensory nature. Similarly, in zebrafish, CFs carry sensory inputs from the accessory optic system (Hsieh et al., 2014; Félix et al., 2023) and the lateral line system (Zwart lab, unpublished). CFs are also critical for PN physiology that drives their sensory and motor functions. PNs show bursts of activity that are largely preceded by CF inputs (Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015). In addition, large CF inputs and bursts of CF inputs result in large calcium transients in PNs (Miyakawa et al., 1992; Good et al., 2017; Varma et al., 2024). Furthermore, CF inputs occurring within 120 ms of parallel fibre (PF) inputs reliably induce long-term depression (LTD) or long-term potentiation (LTP) at PN-PF synapses, based on the location of PNs in the mammalian cerebellum (Albus, 1971; Marr, 1969; Ito & Kano, 1982; Suvrathan et al., 2016; Herzfeld et al., 2018).

There exists a clear spatial organisation in the connections between the inferior olivary nucleus and the cerebellum (**Fig. 1.3 B**). The IO neurons can be classified as unipolar or multipolar based on their dendritic morphology (**Fig. 1.3 B**, (Félix et al., 2024)). The unipolar IO neurons are located in the ventral-rostral region of the olivary nucleus and project to dorsal-medial cerebellar PNs. On the other hand, multipolar IO neurons are located in the caudal–dorsal region of the olivary nucleus and project to the ventral–lateral cerebellar regions (**Fig. 1.3 B**). Functionally, inferior olivary neurons receive indirect direction-selective visual inputs from accessory visual systems. As a result, the IO neurons are highly directionally tuned (**Fig. 1.3 C**) and relay this tuning to the cerebellum (Stone & Lisberger, 1990; Dunn et al., 2016; Knogler et al., 2019; Félix et al., 2024). IO neurons also relay motor information from the spinal cord to the cerebellum (Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015).

Inferior olivary neurons exhibit spontaneous slow and fast subthreshold activity (Lefler et al., 2020). The fast events occur due to intrinsic properties. The slow events are a result of electrical coupling as the IO neurons retain high levels of gap junction coupling (Condorelli et al., 2000; Takeuchi et al., 2017).

The IO neurons are derived from *ptf1a* and *gsx2* co-expressing neural progenitor cells (Fig. 1.3 D, E). Loss of function mutation in either of the two genes is sufficient to induce a significant reduction in IO neurons, and consequent non-lethal perturbation of CF error information to cerebellar PNs (Fig. 1.3 D, E, (Itoh et al., 2020)). This makes *ptf1a* and *gsx2* mutants very useful tools for perturbing cerebellar computation.

The IO in mammals comprises a heterogeneous population of neurons- inhibitory interneurons and two types of excitatory subtypes- cells with complex arbour and cells that have diffuse and complex arbour (reviewed by De Zeeuw et al., 1998). There is evidence of similar classes of excitatory neurons in the Zebrafish IO- cells with a single dendritic tree and cells which have bi- or tri-polar dendritic trees (Felix e al, 2024). However, inhibitory neurons haven't been reported yet.

The olivo-cerebellar circuit in mammals consists of a tripartite loop that is critical for motor learning. The IO neurons excite PNs which in turn inhibit the DCN neurons. A subset of DCN are the small GABAergic nucleo-olivary neurons that inhibit the IO, thereby making a negative feedback loop (Najac & Raman, 2015). The zebrafish olivocerebellar network is yet to be explored for the occurrence of this loop to understand how microcircuitry of the olivocerebellar loop may have evolved.

exists a class of neurons that are ambiguous (not shown). ro: rostral direction, l: left, r: right, c: caudal, d: dorsal, v: ventral; scale bars 100 μm (reproduced from Félix et al., 2024).

- C.** Inferior olivary neurons are direction-selective and respond to specific or a subset of visual motion. Traces show average calcium activity in a forward-tuned neuron (grey), forward-tuned and clockwise neuron (red), forward-tuned and counter-clockwise neuron (blue), forward-tuned, clockwise and counterclockwise neuron (green). DS: direction selective, CW: clockwise, CCW: counterclockwise (reproduced from Félix et al., 2024).
- D.** Loss of inferior olivary neurons in *ptf1a* zebrafish mutants (reproduced with permission from Itoh et al., 2020).
- E.** Loss of inferior olivary neurons in *gsx2* mutants (reproduced with permission from Itoh et al., 2020). *Pvalb7* marks the inhibitory PNs.

1.7 Synaptic pruning in the central and peripheral nervous system during early vertebrate development

During early postnatal development, synaptic density in the central and peripheral nervous system follows an interesting trajectory. Initially, the axon growth is guided by a combination of growth factors, spatiotemporal and mechanosensory cues, steering them towards the regions of maximal activity. This establishes a blueprint of the nervous system during embryonic stages. Subsequently, based on neuronal activity induced by environmental cues, a complex molecular orchestration selectively strengthens the synapses. Active synapses are reinforced and the redundant ones are carefully pruned or eliminated (reviewed by [Lichtman & Colman, 2000](#)). As a result, the synaptic density first increases due to extensive synaptogenesis and then declines to roughly 50-60% of peak density (**Fig. 1.4 A**, (Huttenlocher & Dabholkar, 1997)).

Synaptic pruning is an extremely important step in the formation of a functional nervous system. It involves an activity dependent competition between different synaptic partners of a neuron during a developmentally restricted critical window. For example, formation of

ocular dominance columns in the visual cortex elegantly substantiates the activity dependence and critical window for pruning (Wiesel & Hubel, 1965; Hubel et al., 1977). Deprivation of neuronal activity using monocular suturing results in shrinkage of visual cortical regions associated with the occluded eye. Fibres from both eyes initially overlap in layer IV C, with segregation occurring postnatally. Monocular deprivation causes deprived eye terminals to retract more than normal due to competitive disadvantage. Consequently, the afferents from the open eye extend into the territory of the deprived eye (Wiesel & Hubel, 1964). Under normal development, 80% of the cells respond to either of the two eyes and are orientation selective (Hubel & Wiesel, 1959). However, in case of monocular deprivation, only 7% of total cells recorded responded to the deprived eye and all lacked orientation selectivity. And nearly 80% of the cells responded to the normal eye and also showed direction selectivity. (Wiesel & Hubel, 1964). Furthermore, earlier deprivation resulted in more severe effects, consistent with the critical window hypothesis.

It is hypothesised that the elimination of redundant synaptic partners occurs via a punishment-protection model (**Fig. 1.4 B**). Based on this model, asynchronous activity between different synaptic partners results in a local protection signal at the active synapses and a diffusible punishment signal that spreads to the inactive synapses and destabilises them (**Fig. 1.4 B**, (Lichtman & Colman, 2000)). As a consequence, there is continuous competition between all the synaptic partners, resulting in the survival of the maximally active partner neuron.

For example, olfactory mitral cells undergo activity-dependent dendritic pruning to establish connections with distinct populations of presynaptic olfactory sensory neurons, leading to the formation of odor receptive fields. This study has identified levels of RhoA GTPase activity as a candidate punishment-protection signal (Fujimoto et al., 2023). Similarly, *Arc/Arg3.1*, an early immediate gene has been identified as a moderator of activity-dependent pruning of excess CFs from PNs (Mikuni et al., 2013). In the visual system, right amount of activity dependent synaptic pruning may facilitate the development of the dominance columns which is essential for binocular vision and orientation selectivity in the cortical neurons (Wiesel & Hubel, 1965; Hubel et al., 1977). At the neuromuscular junction, innervation of each muscle fiber by a single motor neuron allows a controlled muscle contraction (Balice-Gordon & Lichtman, 1994). In this study, I will address the functional implications of CF-PN pruning in the cerebellum.

1.8 Pruning of some synapses is tractable due to resultant mono-innervation

The sheer number of synapses in the nervous system makes it extremely challenging to track synaptic pruning. However, some synapses undergo a characteristic remodelling from poly-innervated to mono-innervated configuration. This includes the neuromuscular junction (NMJ) in the peripheral nervous system. At the time of birth, each muscle fibre is innervated by multiple motor neurons. However, activity-dependent competition between different motor neurons results in mono-innervation of muscle fibres (Balice-Gordon & Lichtman, 1994). Furthermore, enhancing inter-synaptic competition by disrupting gap junctional coupling between the competing motor neurons accelerates muscle mono-innervation (Personius et al., 2007). In the central nervous system, postnatal mono-innervation is seen between the retinal projections to the lateral geniculate nucleus and CF projections to the cerebellar PNs. When the inferior olivary nucleus is synchronised, the extent of competition reduces and results in sustained poly-innervation of PNs (Andjus et al., 2003). Just like the formation of ocular dominance columns and NMJ, the PN mono-innervation is also an activity-dependent process and is orchestrated by complex molecular and cellular pathways including the voltage-gated calcium channels and canonical mGluR signalling (**Fig. 1.4 C**, reviewed by Kano et al., 2018). The functional implications of CF pruning remain understudied so far. I will discuss my findings on the functional implications of CF pruning (which remain understudied so far) in [Chapter 2](#).

Chapter 2: Developmental synaptic pruning in the olivo-cerebellar circuit

The work presented in this chapter is available as a preprint on BioRxiv (Verma, S., Narayanan, S. & Thirumalai, V (2024). Developmental synaptic pruning in the olivo-cerebellar circuit sculpts sensori-motor encoding and predictive processing ([Link](#))

2.1 Introduction

The refinement and maturation of the nervous system rely on effective synaptic pruning (1–4). During development, synapses are first overgrown with the help of embryonic cues and then selectively pruned (5), with an estimated 50% of synapses being lost during human brain development (6, 7). This phenomenon of synaptic overgrowth and pruning is seen in the periphery as well as the central nervous system and across different species (8). While the molecular and cellular processes driving developmental synaptic pruning have been studied extensively (9, 10), the functional implications of this process for neural computation and behavior remain largely unexplored.

In the cerebellum, Purkinje neurons (PNs) receive excitatory inputs from parallel fibers (PFs) of granule cells and climbing fiber (CF) axons that originate from neurons of the inferior olivary nucleus. The CF to PN synapse is one of the strongest excitatory synapses known in vertebrates and triggers a large calcium influx into PNs (11, 12). At birth, each PN, receives input from multiple CFs that are then pruned during post-natal life such that every PN is innervated by only a single CF. The transition of mammalian PNs from poly- to mono-innervation is a closely orchestrated activity-dependent process involving cross-talks between the CF-PN synapses and the PF-PN synapses, metabotropic glutamate receptors, voltage-dependent calcium channels and several retrograde and anterograde signaling pathways (13, 14).

Classical cerebellar learning models have underscored the role of CFs as the teaching signal in motor learning (15–17). More recently, studies have shown that CFs encode motor kinematics, sensory variables, and errors in sensory predictions, decisions, and rewards during a variety of learning tasks (18–25). Recently, we showed that CFs encode

predictions and prediction errors which enable faster behavioral responses (22). Yet, how these representations emerge during development or how developmental elimination of CFs affects PN tuning in these contexts have not been explored. In mammals, where most of these studies were performed, CF synapse elimination occurs during stages when motor behaviors are largely absent. This precludes our ability to understand the effect of CF synapse elimination on behavioral output. Zebrafish larvae afford an ideal model for studying functional outcomes of CF synapse elimination due to their fast development into independent organisms with a variety of motor behaviors (26, 27), conserved cerebellar circuitry (28) and accessibility to quantitatively measure neural activity and behavioral parameters. We asked whether the process of CF-PN synapse elimination is conserved in zebrafish and if so, how this affects predictive processing in PNs and behavioral outcomes.

2.2 Results

2.2.1 CF inputs to PNs undergo developmental changes consistent with pruning

Cerebellar PNs receive contralateral inputs from the inferior olivary nucleus via climbing fibers (CFs) (**Fig. 2.1A**). We evaluated CF inputs to PNs during the first two weeks of development, focusing on early (4-5 dpf) and late (11-14 dpf; up to 19 dpf for fictive swim experiments) larval stages, while assessing intermediate stages (7-8 dpf) in some experiments (**Fig. 2.1B**). CF inputs to PNs in larval zebrafish can be easily distinguished in whole-cell voltage clamp and current clamp recordings as well as loose patch extracellular recordings due to their large amplitude and stereotypical kinetics (29) (**Fig. 2.1C**). We recorded spontaneous synaptic currents from PNs in awake larval zebrafish in early and late stages and found that CF inputs in late stage larvae have reduced frequency compared to early stages, as reported in our previous study as well (29) (**Fig. 2.1C, D**). Further, we also observed that the CF excitatory postsynaptic currents (EPSCs) were less variable in amplitude in the late stages compared to the early stages (**Fig. 2.1C**). This was borne out by the coefficient of variation (CV) of EPSC amplitudes (**Fig. 2.1E**). We hypothesized that the high frequency of CF inputs seen in PNs at the early stage could be due to poly-innervation by multiple CFs and the varying synaptic strength between synapses formed by multiple fibers can explain the large amplitude CV observed in early

stage PNs. In the later stages, synaptic pruning proceeds via the selective strengthening and stabilization of a single fiber and progressive weakening and elimination of all the others (9). Consistent with this view, when we normalized EPSC amplitudes to the maximal amplitude within each cell, we found that in early-stage larvae, EPSCs were of small, medium and large amplitudes, whereas at later stages, large amplitudes predominated (**Fig. 2.1F**). The distribution of amplitudes changed such that in early-stage larvae, 20.63% of the pooled amplitudes were less than half of the peak value while in late-stage larvae, this fraction dropped to 7.91% (**Fig. 2.1G**). In addition, the EPSC amplitudes were found to be significantly higher in the late larval stage, although with small effect sizes (**Fig. S2.1B**). These results point us towards developmental pruning of CF to PN synapses. Nevertheless, we considered alternate possibilities as well.

The CF to PN synapse shows short term depression due to its high release probability (30–32). It is possible that the developmental changes in EPSC amplitude variability arise from changes in short term plasticity at these synapses. We probed this angle by first excluding events that occurred within 200 ms. The increase in CF EPSC amplitudes and the decrease in CV of amplitudes persisted even after these events were excluded from our analysis (**Fig. S2.1A, C**). Next, we tested this possibility directly by measuring the paired pulse depression (PPD) at these synapses across these developmental stages. We stimulated CFs with two maximal intensity current pulses at interstimulus intervals (ISIs) of 30, 35 and 50 ms, while recording evoked EPSCs from PNs (**Fig. S2.2A**). At these ISIs, the paired pulse ratio (see methods) is less than 1, indicating short term depression at the CF to PN synapse (32). While the PPR increased with increasing ISIs as would be expected, there was no effect due to the developmental stage (**Fig. S2.2B**).

The decrease in CF EPSC frequency might also result from changes in the spontaneous firing rates of inferior olivary neurons. Using loose-patch electrophysiology, we recorded spontaneous spikes from the soma of the olivary neurons in semi-intact ventral-up preparations of transgenic *hspGFFDMC28C:Gal4; UAS-GFP* larvae at early and late stages (**Fig. S2.2C**, see Methods). The average spontaneous firing rates of olivary neurons showed no significant differences between early and late larval stages (**Fig. S2.2D**).

Taken together, the above results suggest that PNs are poly-innervated by CFs in early-stage larvae which could then get pruned to mono-innervation by later stages, consistent with observations in previous studies (29, 33).

Figure 2.1 CF to PN synapses show signatures of pruning during the first two weeks of larval development in zebrafish.

- A.** Schematic of the olivo-cerebellar circuit (highlighted) in larval zebrafish. Insets: Inferior olivary neurons and their climbing fiber projections (yellow, labelled in a transgenic *hspGFFDMC28C:gal4, UAS:gfp* larva) superimposed with cerebellar Purkinje neurons (pink, labelled using *Ca8-cfos* promoter-enhancer/ *Parvalbumin*). Scale bars 20 μ m.
- B.** Developmental stages investigated in the current study: 4-5 dpf (also referred to as early larval stage, green), 7-8 dpf (also referred to as intermediate larval stage, grey) and 11-14 dpf (also referred to as late larval stage, purple).

- C.** Top: Schematic of *in vivo* whole-cell patch-clamp recording in PNs. Inset: PN filled with sulforhodamine after the recording. Scale bar 20 μm . Bottom: Representative voltage-clamp recordings of spontaneous CF excitatory postsynaptic currents (EPSCs) from a single PN from an early (top, green) and late (bottom, purple) stage larva.
- D.** Reduction in spontaneous CF input frequency (Hz) from early to late developmental stages. Median \pm IQR : 0.4 ± 0.229 (early), 0.286 ± 0.216 (late) (Welch's t-test, $P = 0.01$, Cohen's $d = 0.58$).
- E.** Reduction in coefficient of variation (CV) of CF EPSC amplitudes. Median \pm IQR : 0.256 ± 0.262 (early), 0.078 ± 0.223 (late) (Welch's t-test, $P = 0.004$, Cohen's $d = 0.64$).
- F.** Heatmap showing the spread of CF EPSC amplitudes (normalised to largest amplitude recorded for each PN). Each row shows the fractional distribution of normalized EPSC amplitudes from one cell.
- G.** Reduction in amplitudes that were less than half of the maximum amplitude from early (20.631%) to late (7.91%) developmental stage (pooled data from panel G). Red dashed line indicates half of the maximum amplitude.

Holding potential: -55mV . Recording duration 45 - 180 s. $N = 40$ and 42 cells (from 34 and 40 larvae) for early and late stages, respectively. Colours green and purple represent early (4-5 dpf) and late (11-14 dpf) larval stages, respectively. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$.

Figure S2.1 Developmental changes in spontaneous CF inputs to PNs are independent of short-term depression

- A.** Coefficient of variation (CV) for spontaneous CF EPSCs that are spaced by at least 200 ms from the previous EPSC. Median \pm IQR: 0.202 \pm 0.225 (early), 0.063 \pm 0.174 (late) (t-test, $P = 0.001$, Cohen's $d = 0.73$).
- B.** Pooled amplitudes of all spontaneous CF EPSCs recorded from all PNs. Median \pm IQR : 320.758 \pm 234.027 (early), 383.16 \pm 250.369 (late) (Welch's t-test, $P = 1.2e-10$, Cohen's $d = 0.29$).
- C.** Pooled CF EPSC amplitudes that are spaced by at least 200 ms from the previous EPSC. Median \pm IQR : 345.767 \pm 243.107 (early), 401.269 \pm 238.813 (late) (Welch's t-test, $P = 8.6e-12$, Cohen's $d = 0.35$)

Holding potential: -55mV. $N = 40$ and 42 cells (from 34 and 40 larvae) for early and late stages, respectively. Colours green and purple represent early (4-5 dpf) and late (11-14 dpf) larval stages, respectively. ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$, ns $P > 0.05$.

2.2.2 Functional confirmation of CF to PN synaptic pruning

Innervation status of Purkinje neurons by CFs was systematically assessed using electrical stimulus of gradually increasing intensities (4). We performed field stimulation of CFs with graded current intensities and simultaneously recorded evoked EPSCs from PNs using whole-cell voltage-clamp (**Fig. 2.2A**). Brief current pulses were delivered to create a local electric field at the entry point of CFs into the cerebellum (**Fig. 2.2A**). A full range of current intensities from 100% failure to maximal EPSC amplitude in all trials was tested

(**Fig. 2.2B**). At low intensities, stochastic stimulation of single CFs allowed recruitment of individual fibers. As a result, graded response was seen in the form of multiple discrete amplitudes of CF EPSCs (also referred to as CF steps), corresponding to the different synaptic strengths of the innervating fibers. Whereas, in mono-innervated PNs, the responses were either failures or EPSCs of a single amplitude (single steps) (**Fig. 2.2B**, bottom). At high intensities, a single step was seen due to maximal stimulation of the CFs in both poly- and mono-innervated PNs (**Fig. 2.2B**).

Upon sampling across larval development, we found a mixed distribution of poly- and mono-innervated PNs, with an increase in mono-innervation over development (**Fig. 2.2C**). During the early larval stage, two or more CF steps (poly-innervation) were seen in 10 out of 16 PNs (62.5%), compared to 11 out of 17 PNs (64.5%) in the intermediate larval stage and 5 out of 16 PNs (31.25%) in the late larval stage (**Fig. 2.2C**). While the number of steps represents an absolute measure of CFs associated with a PN, it doesn't account for the varying strengths with which individual CFs are connected to poly-innervated PNs. We used two metrics to quantify the relative strengths of the innervating CFs. The 'innervation index' takes a value equal to 1 for mono-innervated PNs and higher values for poly-innervated PNs. In poly-innervated PNs, with a dominant and strong CF and other weaker inputs, the innervation index takes values close to 1. In cases where the inputs have comparable strengths, the innervation index takes values that are higher than 1. We observed that the innervation indices decline from early (1.299 ± 0.613) to intermediate larval stage (1.152 ± 0.221) with an effect size of 0.4 (**Fig. 2.2D**). Notably, a shrinkage of 63.94% in the interquartile range during this period brings the intermediate innervation indices closer to 1 (**Fig. 2.2D**). This decline continues into the late stage, resulting in a significant reduction from early larval stage with an effect size of 1.27 (**Fig. 2.2D**). We used a second measure, the amplitude disparity index, to ask how different the largest and the second largest EPSC amplitudes were in PNs that had at least 2 steps (see Methods). As expected, the amplitude disparity index increased from early to late stages demonstrating that in late-stage larvae, those PNs that had 2 steps, had one dominant CF input, while the other fiber was severely weakened (**Fig. 2.2E**).

Figure 2.2 PNs transition from poly-innervation to mono-innervation by CFs during the first two weeks of life.

- A.** Top: Schematic of electrophysiological assay for innervation status. PNs are recorded *in vivo* in whole-cell patch-clamp mode with simultaneous electrical stimulation of climbing fibers (red lightning bolt). Inset: A patched PN with CF stimulation using bipolar electrode (red) placed at the edge of the cerebellum. Bottom: Evoked CF EPSC (black) recorded from a PN using a 100 μ s current pulse (red).
- B.** Representative traces of evoked CF EPSCs recorded from a poly-innervated PN with multiple discrete amplitude steps (top) and a mono-innervated PN with single amplitude step (bottom). Superimposed trials are shown for each intensity. Graded current intensities between 10 - 480 μ A were used. For each intensity, a series of ten pulses, 100 μ s long, were delivered at a frequency 0.2 Hz.
- C.** Discrete frequency distribution histograms for evoked CF EPSC amplitude steps recorded from PNs over development (Welch's one-way ANOVA, $P = 0.021$).
- D.** Reduction in innervation index over early development. Median \pm IQR : 1.299 \pm 0.613 (early), 1.152 \pm 0.221 (intermediate), 1 \pm 0.04 (late) (One-way ANOVA for multiple comparisons ($P = 0.006$) followed by post hoc pairwise t-test with Holm-Bonferroni).

correction for early vs intermediate ($P = 0.257$, Cohen's $d = 0.4$), intermediate vs late ($P = 0.047$, Cohen's $d = 0.82$), early vs late ($P = 0.003$, Cohen's $d = 1.27$)).

E. Left: Developmental increase in disparity index for evoked CF EPSCs in poly-innervated PNs (shown in panel D). Right: Representative traces showing differential amplitude disparity between evoked CF EPSCs in poly-innervated neurons. Median \pm IQR : 2.112 \pm 1.062 (early), 5.242 \pm 3.914 (intermediate), 8.396 \pm 11.878 (late) (Kruskal Wallis test for multiple comparisons ($P = 0.022$) followed by pairwise Mann-Whitney U test with Holm-Bonferroni correction for early vs intermediate ($P = 0.339$, Cohen's $d = 0.8$), intermediate vs late ($P = 0.339$, Cohen's $d = 1.04$), early vs late ($P = 0.007$, Cohen's $d = 1.68$)).

Holding potential: -55mV. N = 16, 17, 16 cells (from 11, 17, 13 larvae) for early, intermediate, late stages, respectively. Colours *green*, *grey* and *purple* represent early (4-5 dpf), intermediate (7-8 dpf) and late (11-14 dpf) larval stages, respectively. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, ns $P > 0.05$.

Based on the above, we can conclude that at early larval stages, PNs are predominantly poly-innervated by CFs of comparable strengths, while at late larval stages, PNs are predominantly mono-innervated. Even when innervated by more than one CF in the late larval stage, there is a clearly strong input with the other one being relatively weak and less influential.

Figure S2.2 Firing rate and release probability of presynaptic CFs do not change during the first two weeks of larval development.

- A.** Top: Schematic of *in vivo* whole-cell patch-clamp recording from PNs with simultaneous paired-pulse stimulation of CFs using a bipolar electrode. Bottom: Interstimulus intervals (ISIs) of 30 ms, 35 ms, and 50 ms were used to assess the presynaptic release probability at the CF- PN synapses. Evoked CF EPSCs were recorded from PNs. Paired pulse ratio was calculated as the ratio of second to first evoked CF EPSC amplitude from 3-10 trials.
- B.** Top: Representative traces of CF EPSCs evoked by paired stimulus pulses at an ISI of 35 ms for early (left, green) and late (right, purple) larval stages (Holding potential: -55mV). Bottom: Paired Pulse Ratios (PPR) for early and late larval stages at 30 s, 35 s, 50 s. ISI significantly improved the model ($P < 0.001$) whereas no significant effect of developmental stage was seen on PPR ($P = 0.559$) using linear mixed-effects model with ANOVA. $N = 10, 11$ cells (from 10, 11 larvae) for early and late stages, respectively.
- C.** Left: Schematic of loose-patch recording from the somata of inferior olivary neurons in a ventral-up preparation. Right: Inferior olivary (IO) neurons tagged with green

fluorescent protein in a transgenic *hspGFFDMC28C:gal4; UAS:gfpm* larva. Targeted loose-patch recordings were performed from IO neurons. Scale bar 20 μm .

D. Left: Representative loose-patch recordings performed from early (top, green) and late (bottom, purple) stage larvae. Right: Mean spike frequency (Hz) for individual IO neurons does not change between early and late developmental stages. Median \pm IQR : 0.48 ± 0.316 (early), 0.293 ± 0.371 (late) (Mann-Whitney U test, $P = 0.281$, Cohen's $d = 0.43$). $N = 17, 19$ cells (from 10, 8 larvae) for early and late stages, respectively.

Colours green and purple represent early (4-5 dpf) and late (11-14 dpf) larval stages, respectively. ns $P > 0.05$.

2.2.3 Pruning affects the precision, salience and latency of sensory-motor error

Zebrafish larvae stabilize themselves in slowly moving water bodies by generating swims to compensate for optic flow, in a behavior called the optomotor response (OMR) (34–36). In head-restrained larvae, OMR can be reliably induced by presenting black and white gratings and coupling grating movement to larval swims in a closed loop (22, 37). When grating movement is uncoupled from larval swims (open loop), larvae sense the mismatch between their visual sensory input and motor output and cease to generate swims for several minutes (38). CFs are known to carry error signals when animals encounter a sensory-motor mismatch (39–42).

As a first step towards understanding the functional relevance of pruning, we induced a sensory-motor error by presenting 'open loop' optic flow that lacks visual feedback (27). As the larvae engaged with the optic flow, we recorded the CF inputs from single PNs using whole-cell patch-clamp alongside fictive swim bouts from the ventral nerve cord (**Fig. 2.3A**). When larvae detect that their motor output is ineffective (open loop instead of closed loop), they adjust swim bout parameters even within their very first bout (27), approximately within 300 ms of bout start. Therefore, we looked at this time window relative to bout start to ask whether CF inputs are present and if they are developmentally modulated.

We observed an increase in the frequency of CF inputs around initiation of swim bouts in both early and late larval stages (**Fig. 2.3B, C**). Upon examining individual swim bouts, we found $33.33\% \pm 26.72$ (early stage) and $26.47\% \pm 34.145$ (late stage) of them were accompanied by at least one CF input within 300 ms window from swim start, which we refer to as the motor window (**Fig. S2.3A**). The late stage PNs see a peak CF probability at 95 ms, which is a physiologically relevant latency for cerebellar plasticity and motor learning (see Discussion) (43–45). However, in early stage PNs, this peak occurs with a much longer delay of 205 ms from swim onset (**Fig. 2.3D**). Additionally, late stage PNs also showed a temporally locked elevation in frequency with a peak full width at half max of 380 ms, compared to 656 ms in early stage PNs (**Fig. 2.3D**). Furthermore, peak CF probability around motor start increased by 50.388% in the late stage (**Fig. 2.3D**). Collectively, these results suggest that when there is sensory motor mismatch leading to an olivary error signal, the error is conveyed with greater precision, higher fidelity and improved salience in the later stage mono-innervated PNs compared to the early-stage poly-innervated PNs.

Since there are differences in basal CF frequencies between early and late stages, we compared the specific modulation of CF inputs during the motor window relative to comparable time windows before and after bout start within the respective stages (**Fig. 2.3E, top**). We normalized CF EPSCs to their maximal amplitudes and used a threshold of 0.8 to designate events as large or small. In both early- and late-stage larvae, there was a significant up-modulation of large amplitude CF EPSCs in the motor window compared to the time windows before or after it, of similar durations. However, in the case of the small amplitude events, late-stage larvae showed no modulation while early-stage larvae showed an increase in the frequency of these events in the motor window and in the period following it (**Fig. 2.1F**).

Early-stage larvae tend to have bouts that are longer in duration compared to late-stage larvae (**Fig. S2.3B, (46)**). We wondered if the up-modulation of small amplitude CF EPSCs could be due to bouts that are ongoing. To investigate this angle, we looked at the percent bouts with at least one CF input and found no significant differences (**Fig. S2.3A**). In addition, we analyzed the timing of CF inputs within the motor window for short and long bouts in early-stage and for bouts in the late-stage larvae. Again, we detected no significant differences, indicating that the differences in error encoding between early- and late-stage larvae cannot be attributed directly to differences in the bout duration.

From the above, we can conclude that in early-stage larvae, due to the preponderance of many CF inputs of diverse strengths, the precision, salience and latency of reporting a sensory-motor mismatch are compromised.

Figure 2.3 Improved fidelity and temporal precision of sensori-motor mismatch signals in PNs after synaptic pruning.

- A.** Schematic of fictive motor recording combined with *in vivo* whole-cell patch-clamp recordings from PNs during optic flow (open loop) presentation. Optic flow consisted of seven trials, each with 10 s stationary followed by 10 s forward-moving gratings. The experiment was performed using current-clamp first and then repeated with voltage-clamp (Holding potential: -55mV) for each cell. Amplitude analysis was performed using voltage-clamp data, while frequency analysis included both current-clamp and voltage-clamp recordings.
- B.** Representative traces of voltage-clamp recordings from a PN along with simultaneous fictive swims (pink) in early (top, green) and late (bottom, purple) stage larvae.
- C.** Raster plots showing CF inputs around the onset of swim bouts in early (left) and late (right) stage larvae. Dashed red line at 0 marks the start of motor bouts. Ticks on

y-axis separate different PNs. Each row is one swim bout. Duration of swim bouts (up to 2s) is shaded in pink.

- D.** Gaussian Kernel Density Estimate (KDE) of CF inputs around swim bout onset (red dashed line), with data pooled from all bouts shown in panel C. Open circles and horizontal lines in the respective KDE plots indicate peak CF density and full width at half maximum for early and late stage larvae. Shaded pink region is the motor window and vertical black lines represent the start and end of the pre and post motor window, respectively (described further in panel E (top)).
- E.** Top: Time around swim onset is divided into pre (-300 ms to 0 ms), motor (0 ms to 300 ms), post (300 ms to 600 ms) window to further evaluate the nature of CF inputs associated with motor error. Bottom: Scatter plot showing time of occurrence of CF EPSCs versus their normalized amplitudes. CF EPSCs were categorized as large or small using a threshold of 0.8 (black dashed line), based on the amplitude distribution in Fig. 1F. Vertical black lines mark the start and end of the pre and post motor window, respectively and the pink region indicates the motor window.
- F.** Left: Large CF EPSCs exhibit a motor window specific increase in frequency (Hz) for both developmental groups. Mean \pm sem (pre, motor, post): 0.354 ± 0.09 , 0.855 ± 0.137 , 0.537 ± 0.11 (early); 0.579 ± 0.196 , 1.101 ± 0.2 , 0.342 ± 0.095 (late). Right: Sustained elevation in the frequency of small CF EPSCs beyond the motor window during the early larval stage. Mean \pm sem (pre, motor, post): 0.362 ± 0.109 , 1.212 ± 0.38 , 0.939 ± 0.284 (early); 0.067 ± 0.032 , 0.067 ± 0.024 , 0.052 ± 0.041 (late) (Friedman test for multiple comparisons, $P = 0.0167$, 0.002 (large amplitudes for early and late stages, respectively), 0.039 , 0.676 (small amplitudes for early and late stages, respectively)). Post hoc pairwise comparisons were performed using one-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank test with Holm-Bonferroni correction was used to test the increase in CF frequency from pre to motor and post windows, as well as decrease in CF frequency from the motor to post window).

N = 17, 19 cells (from 16, 19 larvae) for early and late stages, respectively. Colours *green* and *purple* represent early (4-5 dpf) and late (15-19 dpf) larval stages, respectively. Red dashed line indicates the onset of swim bouts. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, ns $P > 0.05$.

Figure S2.3 Frequency of CF inputs to Purkinje neurons (PNs) at bout onset is independent of bout duration

- A.** Percentage of total bouts during single-cell recordings that resulted in at least one CF input during the 300 ms motor window (described in Fig. 3E (top)). Median \pm IQR : 33.333 \pm 26.723 (early), 26.47 \pm 34.145 (late) (Mann-Whitney U test, $P = 0.59$, Cohen's $d = 0.14$).
- B.** Durations of bouts that resulted in at least one CF input during the motor window. Median \pm IQR : 1.117 \pm 2.347 (early), 0.207 \pm 0.47 (late) (t-test, $P = 2.3e-09$, Cohen's $d = 0.62$). Black dashed line marks the threshold (calculated as the 95th percentile of bout durations in late stage larvae) for classification of bouts as short and long.
- C.** Timing of CF inputs recorded in PNs during the motor window for long and short bouts (Data pooled from swim bouts shown in panel B). Median \pm IQR : 0.149 \pm 0.146 (short bouts, early stage), 0.160 \pm 0.122 (long bouts, early stage), 0.126 \pm 0.116 (short bouts, late stage) (Welch's one-way ANOVA, $P = 0.053$).
- $N = 17, 19$ cells (from 16, 19 larvae) for early and late stages, respectively. Colours green and purple represent early (4-5 dpf) and late (15-19 dpf) larval stages, respectively. Red dashed line indicates the onset of swim bouts. *** $P < 0.001$, ns $P > 0.05$.

2.2.4 Late stage PNs receive direction-selective CF inputs

The optomotor stimulus is directional and therefore, any error conveyed to PNs should also be directional if error correction is to be achieved. Indeed, it is known that in mammals complex spikes in Purkinje neurons, triggered by olivary inputs are directionally tuned (43, 47, 48). Recently, such direction selectivity in visual input was also shown in zebrafish inferior olivary neurons (19). We wondered if the deficits in error encoding of the

early-stage larvae during open loop OMR could result from poor directional tuning of CF inputs to PNs. We hypothesised that when larvae encounter optic flow in different directions, a poly-innervated PN would likely receive CF inputs for multiple directions, due to convergence of more than one direction selective CFs. In contrast, a mono-innervated PN with a one-to-one CF mapping would receive a single, direction-specific input. To test this, we presented optic flow in eight different directions and simultaneously recorded CF inputs from single PNs using loose-patch electrophysiology (**Fig. 2.4A**). Over development, we identified mixed PN populations receiving varying degrees of direction-selective CF inputs, ranging from highly selective to completely non-selective (**Fig. 2.4B**). We computed a preference index (PI) for each direction (**Fig. 2.4C**) (see Materials and Methods) and a direction selectivity index (DSI) for every PN as the vector sum of PIs (corresponding to the eight directions) divided by the sum of the magnitude of PIs (see Materials and Methods). A PN receiving CF inputs only for a single direction will have a DSI of 1, whereas if it receives CF inputs equally for all eight directions, the DSI will be 0. We found a mixed distribution of DSIs over development, with a gradual shift towards 1 (**Fig. 2.4D, E**). The late stage PNs showed significantly higher DSIs as compared to early stage with an effect size of 0.96 (**Fig. 2.4E**). These results are consistent with the idea that in early-stage larvae, due to poly-innervation of PNs, directional error information from the inferior olive is corrupted by other CF inputs leading to less precise representations of error.

Figure 2.4 CF EPSCs in PNs show greater directional selectivity to visual stimuli during late larval stages

- A.** Top: Schematic of loose-patch recording from PNs during optic flow (open loop) presentation in eight different directions- left, forward-left, forward, forward-right, right, backward-right, backward, backward left. Bottom: Trial structure for directional stimulus. Directional optic flow was organized into five blocks, with each block containing eight trials, each corresponding to one of the eight directions chosen randomly. Trials consisted of 5 s stationary followed by 3 sec moving gratings. Direction was switched at the end of the moving phase of each trial.
- B.** Representative loose-patch recordings from PNs 1.5 s after flow onset. Two PNs are shown- one with direction non-selective CF inputs (left, open circles) and the other with direction selective CF inputs (right, filled circles). These recordings were from 5 and 13 dpf larvae, respectively.
- C.** Preference index (PI) across all eight directions for the two PNs shown in panel B.
- D.** Radial plots showing developmental increase in CF direction selectivity index (DSI) (represented by length of the line for each cell), at resultant angles calculated from the vector sum of PI. Red concentric rings mark the DSI from 0.2 to 1. Each line represents the DSI of a single PN.

E. DSI distributions for three developmental groups. Median \pm IQR : 0.245 \pm 0.201 (early), 0.281 \pm 0.322 (intermediate), 0.462 \pm 0.305 (late) (Kruskal Wallis test for multiple comparisons ($P = 0.003$) followed by pairwise Mann-Whitney U test with Holm-Bonferroni correction for early vs intermediate ($P = 0.363$, Cohen's $d = 0.37$), intermediate vs late ($P = 0.089$, Cohen's $d = 0.45$), early vs late ($P = 0.001$, Cohen's $d = 0.96$)).

$N = 37, 37, 34$ cells (from 19, 17, 17 larvae) for early, intermediate and late stages, respectively. Colours *green*, *grey* and *purple* represent early (4-5 dpf), intermediate (7-8 dpf) and late (11-14 dpf) larval stages, respectively. ** $P < 0.01$, ns $P > 0.05$.

2.2.5 Emergence of decorrelation in CF inputs to PN populations

Thus far, we have shown that representations of sensory input and sensory-motor error are refined during development at the level of single PNs. We next wanted to ask how these changes affect population level encoding. CF inputs cause large calcium transients that can be detected by calcium imaging (**Fig. S2.4A**) (11, 12, 49). Using single plane light sheet microscopy, we imaged GCaMP6s expressing PNs at different developmental stages (Fig. S2.4B). Large calcium transients were used to estimate CF inputs (**Fig. S2.4C**). The spontaneous mean frequency of CF inputs estimated from calcium imaging (**Fig. S2.4C**, 0.255 \pm 0.13 for early and 0.2 \pm 0.111 for late stage, in Hz) was lower than what we measured from electrophysiology experiments (**Fig. 2.1D**, 0.4 \pm 0.229 for early and 0.286 \pm 0.216 for late stage, in Hz). Such an underestimation in frequency is expected due to slow kinetics of GCaMP6s (50). Furthermore, consistent with electrophysiology, we saw a decline in the estimated frequencies over development (**Fig. S2.4B, C**). Late stage PNs exhibited significantly lower mean frequencies than the early stages (effect size = 0.6; comparable to effect size = 0.58 in **Fig. 2.1D**) (**Fig. S2.4C**). These results give us confidence that calcium imaging can pick up differences in population-wide trends in CF inputs to PNs across development.

To assess the correlations in CF inputs among PNs, we computed Jaccard index (JI) between PN pairs from binarized time series of dF/F traces (see Methods). Consistent with previous studies, JI decreased over development, suggesting a developmental

desynchronization of PNs during the pruning window (**Fig. S2.4D, Video S1**) (51). Moreover, we observed that a significantly large number of PN pairs in the late larval stage were perfectly asynchronous (JI ≈ 0) (**Fig. S2.4E**) and the fraction of such pairs increased over development (**Fig. S2.4F**). Thus, developmentally, during the window of CF synaptic pruning, calcium transients in PNs become progressively more decorrelated. This may be to allow for distinct functions of these clusters depending on the nature of signals carried by the winning CF.

Figure S2.4 Population wide specialization of Purkinje neurons (PNs) over early development.

- A.** Representative widefield imaging with simultaneous loose-patch recording from a PN showing large calcium transients associated with CF inputs. Transgenic *aldoca:GCaMP6s; Nacre^{-/-}* larva was used to measure calcium activity in PNs.
- B.** Left: Schematic showing spontaneous light-sheet imaging of calcium activity in PNs. Right, top: Average GCaMP6s calcium activity of PNs in a single plane recording. Scale bar 20 μm . Right, bottom: Representative calcium activity traces from a pair of PNs in early (green) and late (purple) stage larvae.

- C.** Decrease in estimated mean CF input frequency (Hz) over development. Median \pm IQR : 0.255 \pm 0.13 (early), 0.222 \pm 0.133 (intermediate), 0.2 \pm 0.111 (late) (Welch's one-way ANOVA for multiple comparisons ($P = 3.4e-14$) followed by pairwise Welch's t-test with Holm-Bonferroni correction for early vs intermediate ($P = 3.8e-05$, Cohen's $d = 0.33$), intermediate vs late ($P = 0.002$, Cohen's $d = 0.23$), early vs late ($P = 1.2e-14$, Cohen's $d = 0.6$)).
- D.** Jaccard indices for all pairs of PNs from a single lobe of a representative larva in each developmental group.
- E.** Distribution of Jaccard indices calculated from 90 s time series (pooled PN pairs from all larvae for each developmental group). Inset: X-axis zoomed-in from 0 to 0.1 to show an increased occurrence of completely asynchronous pairs in the late larval stage. Asynchronous PN pairs were defined as those with Jaccard index (JI) < 0.01 (One-way ANOVA, $P = 7.5e-09$).
- F.** Increase in fraction of asynchronous PN pairs over development. Median \pm IQR : 0.085 \pm 0.066 (early), 0.135 \pm 0.064 (intermediate), 0.186 \pm 0.045 (late) (Kruskal Wallis test for multiple comparisons ($P = 0.018$) followed by pairwise Mann-Whitney U test with Holm-Bonferroni correction for early vs intermediate ($P = 0.378$, Cohen's $d = 0.38$), intermediate vs late ($P = 0.127$, Cohen's $d = 0.65$), early vs late ($P = 0.025$, Cohen's $d = 1.0$)).

N = 326, 329, 381 cells (from 10, 11, 13 larvae) for early, intermediate and late stages, respectively. Colours green, grey and purple represent early (4-5 dpf), intermediate (7-8 dpf) and late (11-14 dpf) larval stages, respectively. *** $P < 0.001$, ** $P < 0.01$, * $P < 0.05$, ns $P > 0.05$.

2.2.6 Synaptic pruning mediates efficient predictive processing

PNs receive directionally tuned sensory information and sensory-motor error responses from the olive which enables them to instruct motor learning, predictive processing and adaptive behaviors (21, 22, 42, 52). We wondered if the developmental alterations in sensory tuning and sensory-motor error representations as shown above, will lead to behavioral consequences. We showed previously that when repetitive visual stimuli are presented, CF inputs to PNs ramp up in expectation of the arrival of that input. Similarly,

when the expected input does not arrive, CF inputs encode an error in their expectation. Larvae use these predictive signals to learn stimulus patterns and generate swims with a short latency. When this circuit is compromised, larvae lose the ability to adjust swim latency (22). We tested how larvae at different developmental stages perform in this task and what the CF encoding of predictions and prediction errors looks like in PNs.

Towards this, we performed two-photon calcium imaging of PNs while larvae were engaged in a closed loop optomotor behavior with repetitive stimuli interleaved with probe stimuli (**Fig. 2.5A**) (see Materials and Methods). We first identified PNs that were forward or backward-tuned using a random optic flow stimulus set (**Fig. S2.5A, B**, see Methods). Next, we presented pulsatile strong forward optic flow (1 cm/s) with eight repeats to acclimatize the larvae to this stimulus pattern. This was followed by three repeats of a 'probe' stimulus consisting of weak backward flow (-0.064cm/s) (**Fig. 2.5B**). The forward and backward tuned PNs identified earlier (**Fig. S2.5B**) showed a rise in average calcium activity during the acclimatization and probe phase, respectively (**Fig. 2.5C**). Larvae respond with swims to forward optic flow stimuli but not to the probe stimuli (**Fig. 2.5D**). With repetitive forward flow stimuli, intermediate- and late-stage larvae, but not early-stage larvae, were able to modulate their swim latency (**Fig. 2.5E**).

In line with direction selectivity, these calcium transients in forward and backward tuned PNs have been previously attributed to climbing fiber inputs in similar experiments (22). Such responses were present in early-, intermediate- and late-stage larvae. Nevertheless, larvae at these stages differed in two ways: the calcium signal in forward-tuned PNs prior to forward-flow onset is predictive of swim latency in intermediate and late stage larvae. That is, higher the calcium signal in PNs prior to forward flow onset, lower the swim latency. However, such a negative correlation is absent in early stage larvae indicating that PNs poly-innervated by CFs lack the ability to encode the swim latency predictively (**Fig. 2.5F**). Acclimatization to forward flow enhances the response to backward flow during the probe phase in backward-tuned PNs (**Fig. 2.5G**). Baseline response is the response of backward tuned PNs to weak backward flow during the presentation of random flow stimuli in the first block (**Fig. S2.5**). Compared to baseline, the response to the first probe stimulus post acclimatization was significantly enhanced in intermediate- and late-stage larvae. Such enhancement was absent in early-stage larvae (**Fig. 2.5G, H**). The extent of probe enhancement gradually increased, with late stage PNs showing significantly larger values

(effect size = 0.56) compared to the early stage (**Fig. 2.5H**). Similarly, the reliability with which probe enhancement occurred was also increased in late-stage larvae compared to early-stage larvae (**Fig. 2.5I**). In sum, it appears that PNs at stages where they are poly-innervated by CFs are poorly equipped to acquire models of sensory stimuli. They are also poor at detecting errors in stimulus patterns when expectation does not match reality. These deficits imply that early-stage larvae cannot respond quickly to predictable sensory stimuli.

Figure S2.5 Classification of Purkinje neurons (PNs) as forward or backward tuned using multiple linear regression.

- A.** dF/F for PNs classified as forward (top) or backward (bottom) tuned (mean \pm sem). A kernel with fast rise and slow decay was convolved with forward and backward optic flow to get the forward regressor (red, top) and backward regressor (black, bottom),
- B.** respectively. For each larva, the swim speed trace was similarly convolved to get a motor regressor. With the help of these three regressors, multiple linear regression was performed on individual PN's dF/F trace. All cells with $R^2 \geq 0.4$ were classified as forward, backward or motor based on their largest regression coefficient.
- C.** Heat map of dF/F from all cells classified as forward, backward or motor (ordered from top to bottom, separated by white dashed lines) for early, intermediate and late larval stages.

Figure 2.5 CF inputs to PNs shape sensory predictions and contribute to faster swim responses in late larval stages.

- A.** Schematic of two-photon imaging in a closed-loop environment. Average GCaMP6s calcium activity in PNs of a transgenic *aldoca:GCaMP6s* larva imaged using two-photon microscope (top). Scale bar 20 μm .
- B.** Optic flow trial structure. Five blocks of optic flow spaced by 30 - 40 s were presented to the fish. Each block consisted of an acclimatisation phase (8 forward trials, speed 1 cm/s) followed by probe phase (3 backward trials, speed 0.064 cm/s). Each trial consisted of 5 s long stationary, followed by 2 s long moving gratings.
- C.** Average dF/F traces from forward (top) and backward (bottom) tuned PNs during acclimatisation and probe trials at different larval stages.
- D.** Normalised swim speed (between 0 to 1) of early, intermediate and late stage larvae in response to a single block of optic flow.

- E. Average swim latency normalized to the first trial of the acclimatisation phase. Red dashed line indicates no change from the first trial. N = 10, 12, 13 larvae for early, intermediate and late larval stages, respectively. Linear mixed-effects model with ANOVA, including trial number and trial number plus age showed a significant effect of age on swim latency over trials ($P < 0.001$).
- F. Emergence of small but significant negative correlation between swim latency and pre-flow calcium activity in forward tuned PNs over development. Mixed-effects linear models with N = 8, 6, 7 larvae (with at least 3 identified forward tuned PNs) for early, intermediate and late larval stages, respectively.

2.3 Discussion

We have systematically investigated CF to PN synaptic pruning and its effects on PN encoding of sensory input, sensory-motor errors, predictive processing and motor behaviors. By connecting these strands of information, we have been able to demonstrate that poly-innervation of PNs by CFs leads to lower fidelity and temporal precision leading to loss of predictive power. In turn, this compromises the ability of the olivocerebellar circuit to participate in acquiring internal models and in motor planning. Our study demonstrates that immature circuits such as the CF to PN poly-innervated circuits are limited in their ability to convey specific information to downstream partners and therefore to sculpt behaviors at these early stages. Such constraints could form the basis for the inflexible and limited repertoire of behaviors in developing animals.

2.3.1 Synapse elimination in the context of cerebellar development

We show here that in zebrafish, PNs proceed from poly-innervation by CFs to mono-innervation during the first two weeks of life. This is consistent with previous observations in zebrafish (29, 33) and in line with a similar developmental window in mammals (14). We also find a small portion of PNs with more than one CF in the late-larval stage. It is worth noting that a recent study showed that some adult mouse PNs and a large proportion of adult human PNs are innervated by two CFs on two primary

dendritic branches of a single PN (53). We need to establish whether adult zebrafish PNs are indeed innervated by one or two CFs.

In zebrafish, Purkinje neurons are specified by 2.5 to 3 dpf and functional CF inputs can be recorded by 4 dpf (28, 29). A layered cerebellar structure appears, new PNs continue to be born and PNs elaborate their dendritic arbors by 5 dpf. PN neurogenesis and growth of arbors continues at least until 8 dpf (32, 54). During this time, PNs are electrically active and participate in many motor behaviors such as OMR and optokinetic response (22, 29, 42, 55). Thus, in larval zebrafish, the cerebellum seems to be functional, yet under construction during these early larval stages. In the rodent cerebellum, apart from CF synaptic pruning, PNs form transient synaptic connections with each other leading to traveling waves of activity (56, 57). We have not observed PN-PN connections or the traveling wave phenomenon in larval zebrafish. Nevertheless, we wish to point out that the period of synaptic pruning coincides with dramatic changes within the cerebellum, all of which may contribute to fine tuning network computation. Our aim is to showcase the effect of CF to PN synaptic pruning on how PNs receive these inputs and in turn how that impinges on behavior. Similar studies focused on other aspects of cerebellar development during this same period will be necessary to appreciate the full extent of cerebellar metamorphosis.

2.3.2 Widespread synaptic pruning and its implications

Developmental synaptic pruning is widespread- it is known to occur at the neuromuscular junction, in the autonomic nervous system, in the lateral geniculate nucleus and in the neocortex, apart from the cerebellum (1–3, 6, 7, 9). Predictive processing is also widespread within the central nervous system. We and others have shown predictive activity in the cerebellum that contributes to motor planning (22, 52, 58, 59). In the neocortex, predictive and prediction error signals associated with learned associations or repeating patterns of sensory stimuli have been recorded (60). Whether such computations are also affected by developmental synaptic pruning will need to be addressed in the future.

Furthermore, timing of CF is extremely critical for cerebellar plasticity. CF inputs relay sensory-motor error signals to the cerebellar PNs and facilitate motor learning by inducing long term depression at the parallel fibre (PF) synapses (15-17, 44, 45). CF inputs that

precede PF inputs by 120 ms reliably induce long-term depression (LTD) at PN-PF synapses, based on the location of PNs in the mammalian cerebellum. A subset of PNs also failed to show any plasticity when this interval was greater than 150 ms (44). This plasticity is crucial for motor learning. In this study, when we presented optic flow in open-loop environments devoid of visual feedback, motor errors manifested as increase in CF input frequency at the larval swim start. In poly-innervated PNs, the weak and winnowing fibers result in a persistent elevation of CF inputs up to 650 ms from swim start, possibly due to convergence of sensory and motor CFs. However, CF inputs in mono-innervated PNs were more precisely locked with a sharp peak within ~100 ms from the onset of swim bouts. Therefore, elimination of excess fibers fine-tunes the timing of CF errors, reduces noisy inputs and thereby, may facilitate cerebellar plasticity and motor learning.

2.4 Materials and Methods

2.4.1 Biosafety and Ethics

All experiments in this study were performed on larval zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) from 4-19 dpf with approval of the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC) and Institutional Biosafety Committee (IBSC). ZFIN was used as a reference for all zebrafish protocols (zfin.org). The following fish lines were used for different experiments as appropriate: hspGFFDMC28C:gal4; UAS:gfp (Prof. Koichi Kawakami, National Institute of Genetics, Japan) (61); aldoca:GCaMP6s; nacre^{-/-} (Prof. Masahiko Hibi, Nagoya University, Japan); ca8-cfos construct for driving expression in Purkinje neurons (Prof. Hideaki Matsui, Niigata University, Japan) (55).

2.4.2 Animal Maintenance

Adult zebrafish were housed in ZebTec zebrafish housing system (Tecniplast, Italy) at a temperature of 28°C, pH 7.4, conductivity of 1200 µS and 14:10 hrs light-dark cycle. All adult fish were fed twice a day with freshly hatched brine shrimp (Summit Artemia, Great Salt Lake Artemia, USA) in the morning and adult zebrafish diet (Zeigler, USA) in the evening. Evening feed was replaced with freeze dried bloodworms, (Hallofeed, India) twice

a week. Juvenile fish were given the same morning diet plus three feedings of larval AP100 <100 microns (Zeigler, USA) interspersed during the day.

Embryos were rinsed thoroughly and raised in E3 medium treated with 0.36 μ M methylene blue (M9140, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) in 90mm petri dishes (Tarsons Products, India). Up to 15 days post fertilization (dpf), larvae were housed in a 28°C incubator (MIR-154, Sanyo, Japan) with a zeitgeber cycle identical to adults. Developmental synchronization was performed at three stages- (a) 24 hours post fertilization, 5 - 26+ somite stage, (b) 2.5 - 3 dpf, hatched larvae, and (c) 4 dpf, larvae with a visible swim bladder. At this stage, the larvae were transferred to tanks (12 x 8 x 5 cm) for experiments and thereafter, fed with larval AP100 <100 microns four times a day. Population of 25-35 larvae per tank was maintained at all times and E3 medium was replaced every day.

2.4.3 Developmental stages

Three larval stages were used in this study, namely, 4-5 dpf (early larval stage), 7-8 dpf (intermediate larval stage) and 11-14 dpf (late larval stage; up to 19 dpf for fictive swim recordings).

2.4.4 Visualization of CFs and PNs

The inferior olivary nucleus was labelled with green fluorescent protein (GFP) in a transgenic *hspGFFDMC28C:gal4; UAS:gfp* larva. Sparse genetic labelling of olivary neurons was achieved by microinjecting single-celled embryos with *Tol2-UAS:mcherry* plasmid (50 ng/ μ L) and *Tol2* transposase mRNA (100 ng/ μ L) (62). PNs were labelled using *Tol2-ca8-cFos:ecfp* plasmid (50 ng/ μ L for sparse genetic labelling) or immunostained with α -Parvalbumin antibody (mouse-monoclonal, MAB1572, Sigma-Aldrich, USA). Imaging was performed using light-sheet (Zeiss Lightsheet 7) and confocal (FV3000, Olympus, Japan) microscopes. Acquired images were merged in Fiji (63).

2.4.5 Preparation for electrophysiology

Larval zebrafish were anaesthetized using 0.0168% w/v tricaine/ MS-222 (E10521, Sigma-Aldrich, USA). Micro-dissections were performed on live anaesthetized fish under a stereo microscope (SZX16, Olympus, Japan) with oblique illumination. Using short tungsten pins (M249400, California Fine Wire Company, USA, 25.4 mm), fish were positioned laterally on a sylgard (SYLGARD™184 Silicone Elastomer Kit, The Dow

Chemical Company, Germany) base in the center of an in-house custom designed acrylic recording chamber or a transparent 60 mm petri dish (Corning, USA). Two pins were first pushed through the notochord, one at a rostral segment adjacent to the swim bladder and another at a caudal segment. As per the requirement of the preparation (dorsal-up/ventral-up), the head was then rotated, tricaine was washed out with external saline (composition in mM; 134 NaCl, 2.9 KCl, 1.2 MgCl₂, 10 HEPES, 10 Glucose, 2.1 CaCl₂; 290 mOsm, pH 7.8). The pinned larva was then paralyzed by adding a drop of 1 mg/mL α -bungarotoxin (203980, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) dissolved in external saline for 7-10 minutes following which it was washed with external saline. Alternatively, 0.016 mg/mL tubocurarine (T2379, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was used in the external saline throughout the recording. In the dorsal-up preparation, skin from the dorsal side of the brain was peeled using fine forceps (Student Dumont #5, Fine Science Tools, Canada) to expose the cerebellum. In the ventral-up reduced preparation, ventral tissue was gently removed with the help of a tungsten pin and fine forceps just until the brain was accessible. The brain, eyes, and the trunk were kept intact during this procedure (adapted from (64)). The recording chamber containing the larval preparation was placed on a fixed stage (Scientifica, UK).

2.4.6 Single cell recordings

Patch pipettes were made by pulling filamented borosilicate glass (1.5 mm OD, 0.86 mm ID; Harvard Apparatus, USA) using a Flaming/ Brown P97/P1000 puller (Sutter Instrument, USA). Pipettes were backfilled with either of two internal salines to achieve a pipette resistance of ~10 MW: cesium gluconate internal saline (composition in mM: 115 Cs hydroxide, 115 Gluconic acid, 15 CsCl, 2 MgCl₂, 10 HEPES, 10 EGTA, 4 MgATP; 290 mOsm, pH 7.2) was used for voltage-clamp recordings in graded stimulation experiments. For current-clamp and voltage-clamp recordings in open-loop motor experiment, we used K-gluconate internal saline (composition in mM: 115 K gluconate, 15 KCl, 2 MgCl₂, 10 HEPES, 10 EGTA, 4 MgATP; 290 mOsm, pH 7.2). Sulforhodamine (S1402, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) at final concentration of 5 mg/mL was added to the internal saline and filtered using 0.22 μ m filter.

The recording pipette was positioned using a motorized micromanipulator (Double PatchStar, Scientifica, UK). Neurons were approached with the help of a 60x water immersion objective (CFI Fluor 60X, 1.0 NA, Nikon, Japan) on a Nikon microscope (Eclipse FN1 Upright, Nikon, Japan) connected to a Flea3-USB3.0 camera (FLIR, USA).

In voltage clamp experiments, the holding potential was set to -55mV. Passive properties (series resistance, input resistance and input capacitance) were calculated from a 150-200 ms long hyperpolarizing pulse to -80 mV delivered intermittently during the experiment. For all recordings in this study, series resistance was less than 20% of input resistance. Over the course of the experiment, not more than 25% change in series and input resistances was allowed. In addition, recordings were monitored over time to ensure stable CF EPSC amplitudes. Recordings of spontaneous CF EPSCs were performed in the dark for 45 to 180 s. Loose patch recordings were performed as above but with the pipette filled with external saline. Upon establishing a stable seal of 60-100 M Ω , recordings were performed in I=0 mode.

2.4.7 Fictive motor recordings

Suction pipettes were made from non-filamented thin-walled glass (1.5 mm OD, 1.10 mm ID; Harvard Apparatus, USA) pulled to a tip diameter of 30-40 μ m. The pipette was backfilled with external saline and positioned at the inter segmental junction with the help of the camera. Gentle suction was applied and locked to get stable recording from the ventral root of the spinal nerve. All suction recordings were obtained from \pm 2 segments from the cloaca. Spikes with an inter spike interval (ISI) of 1 s were classified into different swim bouts. Bouts with at least 3 spikes were considered for analysis.

2.4.8 Data acquisition and analysis

All electrophysiology data were acquired using Multiclamp 700B amplifier, Axon Digidata 1440A and Axon pCLAMP 10 acquisition software (Molecular Devices, USA) at a sampling rate of 20 - 50 kHz with a low pass filter of 1.8 - 2 kHz. The gain was set to 1 for whole-cells, 200 for loose-patch and 200 - 2000 for fictive swim recordings. Acquired data was stored as .abf files and analyzed post hoc with custom Python scripts. Spike detection for loose-patch recordings was performed using MATLAB functions from the open access

mbl-nsb-toolbox (<https://github.com/wagenadl/mbl-nsb-toolbox>). CFs inputs and simple spikes were distinguished based on their waveform and amplitude.

2.4.9 Graded CF stimulation

Climbing fibers were electrically stimulated in a dorsal up larval preparation with the help of a twisted pair bipolar electrode custom-made using Formvar insulated Nichrome wire (76100, A-M Systems, diameter- 17.78 μ m bare, 25.4 μ m coated). The bipolar electrode was positioned at the lateral tip of the cerebellar lobe and simultaneous whole-cell recording was performed from a single ipsilateral PN (Fig. 2A).

CFs were stimulated at a range of current intensities to create electric fields of varying strengths. Depending on the strength of the electric field and relative distance of a fiber from the center of the field, single action potentials were stochastically elicited and a CF EPSC was recorded in the PN with a latency of 2-5 ms. The number of discrete steps of evoked CF EPSC amplitudes seen in PNs was used as a readout of the innervation. For each current intensity, ten pulses, 100 μ s long, were delivered at a frequency of 0.2 Hz by a stimulus isolator (ISOflex, A.M.P. Instruments, Israel). Maximum and minimum intensities were identified as values at which all ten trials resulted in either the largest possible evoked CF EPSC amplitude (100% success) or no evoked CF EPSC at all (100% failure), respectively. All current intensities between maximum and minimum values were sampled with 10 μ A steps. Sequence of intensities was randomized to prevent effects of short term plasticity. The current intensities ranged between 10 - 480 μ A. Trials with noisy baseline, overlapping EPSCs, or large stimulus artefacts were excluded from analysis.

2.4.10 Innervation index and Disparity index

The innervation index was computed as the sum of CF steps normalized to the maximum step amplitude. This results in an innervation index of 1 for mono-innervated PNs. Values close to 1 suggest poly-innervation dominated by a strong CF alongside weaker CFs, while substantial deviations from 1 indicate poly-innervation with multiple strong CFs.

Disparity index was computed to measure the fold change between the strongest CF EPSC and the weaker ones as follows:

A large disparity index indicates selective strengthening or maintenance of a single CF while weakening the others.

2.4.11 Paired-pulse experiment

Paired pulse experiment was performed by stimulating climbing fibers in a similar configuration as graded stimulation experiment. Initially, maximum intensity (current value that results in 100% success) was identified by delivering five 0.1 ms long pulses at a frequency of 0.2 Hz. Subsequently, maximum intensity trials, each consisting of two pulses separated by an interstimulus interval (ISI) were delivered. Trial frequency of 0.1 Hz and ISIs of 30, 35 and 50 ms were used. In addition to the trial exclusion criteria in the graded stimulation experiment, trials where one or more spontaneous CF EPSCs occurred in the interstimulus interval were also excluded. Paired Pulse Ratio (PPR) was calculated from the EPSC amplitudes evoked by the two current pulses as follows:

For each ISI, we measured the mean PPR from 3-10 trials.

2.4.12 Optic flow presentation

Optic flow consisted of moving black and white gratings with a spatial period of 1 cm on a screen. A custom Processing (www.processing.org) script was used to create the gratings and update their position at a frequency of 120 Hz (which is also the refresh rate of the screen). For experiments with electrophysiology, a 5-inch Raspberry Pi LCD display was used to present whole field optic flow beneath the larva with a pixel size of 0.13 mm. For experiments with two-photon imaging, black and red gratings were projected on a diffusive screen with a pixel size of 0.32 mm, using a modified LCD screen (as described previously in (22)). Each trial of optic flow comprised stationary followed by moving gratings. Duration and direction of moving and stationary phases are indicated in the description of the respective experiments.

2.4.13 Open-loop optic flow presentation with electrophysiology

Fictive motor recordings were obtained from dorsal up-preparations as described above. The objective was then gently moved along the body axis to focus on the cerebellum. Upon securing a stable recording from a single PN, the LCD display mounted on a micromanipulator (MM-3, Narishige, Japan) was gently slid under the recording chamber containing the larval preparation.

For the experiment in Figure 3, optic flow consisted of seven trials of forward moving gratings in an open-loop environment. Each trial was 20 s long, with a 10 s stationary followed by 10 s moving gratings. Simultaneous suction and whole-cell recording with visual stimulus were performed in both voltage- and current-clamp mode. CF frequencies were calculated from both voltage- and current-clamp recordings, while CF amplitude analysis was performed only on voltage-clamp data.

For the experiment in Figure 4, directional optic flow was presented in an open-loop environment to the larvae in dorsal up preparation. The experiment consisted of five blocks of visual stimulus. Each block consisted of eight randomized trials in one of the eight directions, i.e., forward, backwards, left, right, forward left, forward right, backwards left and backwards right. As a result, five trials were presented for each direction. Each trial consisted of a 5 s stationary period followed by a 3 s flow period. Direction was changed at the onset of the stationary phase in each trial. Simultaneous loose-patch recordings were performed from PNs alongside presentation of directional stimulus.

2.4.14 Direction Selectivity Index (DSI)

CF frequency was calculated for each trial in the 1.5 s following flow start. This period is expected to capture sensory associated CF inputs (Fig. 4B). For each direction, Preference Index (PI) was calculated as the product of the mean CF frequency across 5 trials and the fraction of trials with non-zero CF frequency. Direction Selectivity Index (DSI) was computed from PI in vector space:

DSIs range between 0 and 1, where 0 represents a neuron with equal response in all eight directions and 1 represents a neuron that responds only in a single direction (19, 65).

2.4.15 Agarose embedding

Transgenic *aldoca:GCaMP6s; nacre^{-/-}* larvae were first anaesthetized and then paralyzed using 1 mg/mL α -bungarotoxin or 0.016 mg/ml tubocurarine. For light-sheet imaging, larvae were embedded vertically inside a thin glass capillary using 1% low gelling agarose (A9414, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) made in E3 medium and then held in the sample holder of a

light-sheet microscope (Lightsheet 7, Zeiss, Germany). Thereafter, the fish was lowered in a chamber filled with filtered system water and the cerebellum was located.

For two photon imaging, a drop of 2% low gelling agarose made in E3 medium was used to embed the larvae in a transparent 60mm petri dish (Corning, USA) facing dorsal side up. After 20 minutes, the dish was filled with E3 medium. The tail was then freed by carefully removing the agarose around the swim bladder using a surgical blade. The embedded larvae were allowed to acclimatize for 7-10 hours before the experiment.

2.4.16 Light-sheet calcium imaging

Spontaneous activity was imaged for 1.5 minutes in PNs. A single plane was imaged using pivot scan mode with 4-10% of the input laser power (25mW) on the Zeiss Zen Black acquisition software. Dual side (left and right) illumination was performed using a pair of 10x air objectives (LSFM 10x/0.2 foc, Carl Zeiss, USA). Emission was detected orthogonally using a 20x water immersion objective (W Plan-Apochromat, 1.0 NA, Carl Zeiss, USA). Online fusion was carried out from the images captured by left and right illumination. The resulting sampling rate was 25 Hz.

2.4.17 Two-photon imaging of PNs

GCaMP6s was excited using a Titanium:Sapphire laser (Chameleon Ultra II, Coherent Inc, USA), tuned to 920 nm with a peak pulse width of 140 femtoseconds, frequency of 80 MHz and power of up to 30mW at sample. External PreComp (Chameleon, Coherent, USA) placed in the light path was set to zero GVD at 920 nm. ScanImage 3.8 (66) was used to perform time series imaging of a single plane of PNs. A field of view with 512*128 pixels was scanned using a zoom of 1.4 at a frame rate of 7.81 Hz (resultant pixel dwell time of 1.6 μ s). Image acquisition was synchronized with behaviour experiments using a custom Processing script that sends a TTL pulse to ScanImage. In order to acclimatize the larvae to high frequency vibration of XY-scan mirrors, optomotor behaviour experiments were programmed 30 s after the initiation of two-photon imaging. Imaging was performed continuously for up to 15 minutes.

2.4.18 Optomotor behavior

For behaviour experiments performed along with two-photon imaging, a small square shaped window was cut on the projection screen underneath the larva. This allowed high speed video recording of the tail at 200 frames per second (fps) using a Flea3-USB3.0 camera (FLIR, USA). With the help of Bonsai (67), consecutive frames in the video recording were subtracted to get real-time Larval Locomotor Drive (LLD). Open Sound Control (OSC) communication was then used to send LLD to the Processing script, running in parallel. In closed-loop (CL) environments, this Processing script compensates for the larval swims when updating the gratings, while in open-loop (OL) environments, the updates are independent of larval swims.

2.4.19 Estimation of larval swim velocity

During CL behaviour experiments, larvae are allowed to engage with the optic flow. This was done by compensating for the grating movement based on larval swim velocity. To estimate the swim velocity, LLD was scaled to an average velocity of 1.5 cm/s. Scaling factor was calculated by presenting a 10 s long forward optic flow in OL environment to each larva before beginning of close loop experiment, as:

Using this scaling factor, raw-Instantaneous Swim Velocity (ISV_{raw}) was computed for each frame n , as follows:

Thereafter, a rolling exponential smoothing algorithm was implemented to get Instantaneous Swim Velocity (ISV) as follows:

Here, Δt represents the time interval between previous and current frame (equals to roughly 8 ms, resulting from iterations at 120 Hz in Processing). ISV_{n-1} was initialized to 0 for the first frame at the start of the experiment.

2.4.20 Closed loop feedback

Optic flow presentation was structured uniquely by experimentally setting the flow, gain, grating speed, grating direction. For a given frame n , the grating displacement ($d_{\text{grat}})_n$ was computed as:

Displacement of the larva was estimated as:

The updated grating position (Pos_n) was computed by compensating for the larval displacement as follows:

Gain was set to 0 for open loop and 1 for closed loop. Flow was set to 0 for stationary gratings and 1 for moving gratings.

2.4.21 Prediction-error experiment

The experiment was performed in two blocks separated by 30 s. First block consisted of five random repeats for each of the following trial types: forward flow with grating speed of 1 cm/s, forward flow with grating speed of 0.064 cm/s, backward flow with grating speed of 1 cm/s and backward flow with grating speed of 0.064 cm/s. This block was used for classification of cells as forward, backward or motor (Fig. S5A, B). The second block comprised five repeats, each consisting of an acclimatization phase followed by a probe phase (Fig. 5B). During the acclimatization phase, eight forward trials were presented with a grating speed of 1 cm/s. During the probe phase, three backward trials were presented with a grating speed of 0.064 cm/s. The five repeats were separated by an interval of 30-40 s. All trials had 5 s stationary followed by 2 s moving gratings (22).

2.4.22 Extraction and analysis of GCaMP signals

Time series of images acquired from the light-sheet and two-photon microscope were pre-processed in Suite2p (68) by optimizing the parameters for cell detection (Table S1). Motion correction was performed using non-rigid registration in blocks of 128 x 128 (light-sheet) or 64 x 64 (two-photon) pixels. Cellpose (69) anatomical detection method was used to find masks on enhanced mean images. ROIs were detected with a diameter

~6 microns and those with no overlapping pixels were only used for analysis. Semi-automatic identification of cell bodies was performed using Suite2p GUI. Mean neuropil fluorescence (F_{neu}) was estimated using inner neuropil radius equal to soma radii. For each ROI, 0.7 times F_{neu} was subtracted from mean fluorescence value to get frame-wise ROI fluorescence (F) which was then NaN-padded on both ends. Baseline was calculated as the tenth percentile of ROI fluorescence (F) in a 1-minute window around each frame. Fold change in fluorescence from baseline (dF/F) was computed framewise for each ROI as follows:

dF/F trace was smoothed using a Gaussian filter (SciPy `ndimage gaussian_filter1d`, `sigma=3`) for 1P imaging (70).

2.4.23 Calculation of Jaccard index

1.5 minutes long time series light-sheet images were used to compute synchrony between PNs using Jaccard Index. To ensure a good signal-to-noise ratio, cells with at least 20% dF/F were selected. dF/F peaks were detected with the help of the `find_peaks` function in SciPy (70). Peaks were assigned as CF associated calcium transients using a threshold and prominence of 5%. For active cells with 3 or more peaks, the dF/F for all frames from peak minus 200 ms to peak were set to one and the other frames were set to zero, resulting in a binary activity time series. The degree of overlap between a pair of neurons A & B was computed using Jaccard index (intersection over union) with the help of the Scikit-learn Python module (71, 72).

Jaccard index was calculated for all possible pairs of active PNs within a cerebellar lobe for each larva. Pairs with $JI < 0.01$ were assigned as asynchronous.

2.4.24 Classification of PNs as motor, forward or backward tuned

PNs were classified as motor, forward or backward tuned from the first block of stimulus presentations in random order (Fig. S5). Forward and backward regressors were generated by convolving the respective components of the optic flow with the GCaMP kernel, which was modelled as a dual alpha exponential function (Fig. S5A). Similarly, a motor regressor was generated for each larva using the swim velocity. Thereafter, multiple

linear regression was performed to fit the calcium activity of individual PNs to the motor, forward and backward regressors. PNs with $R^2 > 0.4$ were classified as motor-, forward- or backward-tuned based on the largest regression coefficient (Fig. S5B) (22, 49).

2.4.25 Calculation of probe enhancement and reliability score

The Probe Enhancement (PE) index was calculated for all backward tuned PNs using the peak dF/F values from before and after the acclimatization, as given below:

The peak dF/F (Baseline) was calculated as the average response across five backward trials presented at 0.064 cm/s during the first block of the prediction-error experiment (Fig. S5). The peak dF/F (first probe) was calculated as the average response across five trials of the first probe trial during the second block of the experiment (Fig. 5B).

In addition, to assess the fidelity with which probe enhancement was seen upon acclimatization, we computed a reliability score over the five repeats as:

2.4.26 Statistical analysis

Linear mixed-effects model with ANOVA (Figures S2D and 5D) was computed using R. All other statistical tests were performed in Python using SciPy and Statsmodels (70, 73). Distributions were first tested for normality (Shapiro-Wilk test) and homoscedasticity (Levene's or Fligner Test) and then compared using the appropriate parametric or non-parametric tests, as applicable. In cases of multiple comparisons between the three developmental stages, distributions were first compared using ANOVA/ Kruskal Wallis (unpaired) or Friedman test (paired) with a significance threshold of 5% followed by appropriate post hoc pairwise comparisons with Holm-Bonferroni correction (73, 74). Cohen's d (effect size) was computed using Pingouin (75). Whiskers on the box plots represent 1.5 times the interquartile range (IQR).

Author contributions

All experiments, data acquisition and analysis and writing the first draft were done by Shivangi Verma. Sriram Narayanan designed and built the 2 photon system used for calcium imaging.

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Chapter 3: PN neurogenesis during early cerebellar development

3.1 Introduction

In most vertebrates, cerebellar PN neurogenesis is restricted to the embryonic and perinatal stages with limited accessibility. However, due to early-stage hatching, we can access the functional newly born PNs in the developing larvae (Kaslin et al., 2013). The zebrafish cerebellum undergoes massive reorganisation during the first two weeks of larval development. During this phase, in addition to CF elimination (discussed in [Chapter 2](#)) and growth of PN dendrites (Sitaraman et al., 2021), neurogenesis constantly remodels the cerebellar circuit (Hamling et al., 2015; Kaslin et al., 2013). This happens in conjunction with the improvement of motor skills for escape and predation. Between 2.3 to 2.8 dpf, *ptf1a* expressing neuronal progenitor cells in the ventricular zone migrate dorsally and differentiate into cerebellar Purkinje neurons (PNs). As a result, the first PNs are seen at ~2.8 dpf using parvalbumin 7 (Pvalb7) or carbonic anhydrase 8 (Ca8) immunoreactivity (Bae et al., 2009; Hamling et al., 2015; Pose-Méndez et al., 2023). Consequently, the cerebellar architecture is laid out by 4 dpf. This is also when synaptic inputs and intrinsic activity of PNs is established (Hsieh et al., 2014; Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015). As development continues, the cerebellar output is extensively refined during the first two weeks of development via pruning of excessive climbing fibres ([Chapter 2](#)). While the already formed circuit is maturing during this early phase of development, a large number of new PNs are constantly being integrated into the circuit via neurogenesis ([Kaslin et al., 2013](#)). However, the functional integration of new-born PNs in the existing circuit is unclear.

According to findings from Kaslin et al., 2013, neurogenesis in different cerebellar cell types continues during early development. The granule cell (GC) population continues to proliferate for up to seven months and even later, evolutionarily agreeing with other vertebrates (Rueda-Alaña & García-Moreno, 2021). On the other hand, PNs and inhibitory

interneurons continue to proliferate till two months of development but can regenerate in later stages in the event of ablation or injury (Vandestadt et al., 2021). PNs almost double in number within the first two weeks of development (Hamling et al., 2015; Kaslin et al., 2013). However, their real-time functional integration and roles in the cerebellar circuit are unknown. To address this, I first generated a transgenic zebrafish line with PN-specific expression of photo-activable protein Dendra2 (Chudakov et al., 2007). I then birth-dated PNs using UV light-induced photo-conversion and tracked the new-born neurons at early (4-5 dpf), intermediate (7-8 dpf) and late (12-15 dpf) larval stages.

In this study, I have performed an in-depth characterisation of Dendra2 photo-conversion: both localised and complete, in zebrafish PNs. Thereafter, I studied the localisation patterns of new-born neurons and addressed their function in the cerebellum.

3.1.1 Photoactivatable fluorescent proteins (PAFPs)

The discovery and development of green fluorescent protein (GFP) from jellyfish by Roger Y. Tsien, Osamu Shimomura, and Martin Chalfie has been a landmark in the history of science. The chromophore of GFP lies at the centre of its β -barrel- cylindrical part of the 3D structure of GFP. Over the past few decades, a diverse range of fluorescent proteins have either been cloned from different marine organisms (like corals and sea anemones) and/or evolved from GFP by mutagenising the chromophore site. As a result, we have abundant variants of fluorescent proteins with a wide spectral range. These variants have also been engineered to make genetically encoded biological sensors like GCaMP, pHluorin, Voltron and PAFPs (Miesenböck et al., 1998; Nakai et al., 2001; Lukyanov et al., 2005; Abdelfattah et al., 2019). Photo-activatable fluorescent proteins (PAFPs) are fluorescent proteins that change their spectral properties when irradiated with light of specific wavelength, intensity and duration (Lukyanov et al., 2005). They can be genetically encoded to track cells, organelles and fusion proteins. Some examples of PAFPs include Dendra, Kaede, PS-CFP2 and Dronpa (Section 3.1.3). In this study, we have used Dendra2, a monomeric PAFP that is encoded in its green state (Dendra2-green) and irreversibly switches to red state (Dendra2-red) (Chudakov et al., 2007). A broader variety of PAFPs and their evolution are further discussed and reviewed by (Lukyanov et al., 2005).

3.1.2 Dendra2- a monomeric photo-activable protein

Dendra2 was obtained by applying a sequential mutagenesis strategy to dendGFP, a naturally occurring UV-mediated PAFP in octocoral *Dendronephthya sp.* (Labas et al., 2002; Gurskaya et al., 2006; Chudakov et al., 2007). dendGFP was a tetrameric protein and hence it had a slower maturation time. The oligomeric state also made it less suitable for tagging proteins as it can interfere with the natural folding of the target protein. To overcome these challenges, a monomeric variant called Dendra was generated by introducing mutations that disrupt subunit interfaces (Karasawa et al., 2003; Gurskaya et al., 2006). Dendra was further modified to get Dendra2 which had an enhanced brightness at the initial green state as well as the photo-activated red state. This derivative also exhibited a faster maturation time making it readily utilisable for tracking faster processes (Chudakov et al., 2007).

The initial state of Dendra2 naturally exists as an equilibrium between a Dendra2-green (deprotonated) and a non-fluorescent state (protonated). Irradiation with UV light (~400 nm) photo-activates the non-fluorescent state whereas blue light (~488 nm) photo-activates the Dendra2-green. Both result in a decarboxylation event leading to a switch to Dendra2-red (**Fig. 3.3 A**). UV irradiation photo-activates more efficiently than blue light. Consequently, the green state can be easily imaged using a 488 nm laser at low intensity, without photo converting to the red state (Chudakov et al., 2007).

3.1.3 Comparison between different PAFPs

Comparison of common PAFPs				
Properties	Dendra	Kaede	PS-CFP2	Dronpa
Oligomeric state	monomer	tetramer	monomer	monomer
Change in fluorescence upon photo-activation/ photo-conversion	Dual colour (green to red)	Dual colour (green to red)	Dual colour (Cyan to green)	Single colour (non-fluorescent (NF) to fluorescent (F))

Photo-conversion wavelength	~400 nm (UV) ~490 nm (blue)	~400 nm (UV)	~400 nm (UV)	~400 nm (UV) NF>F ~488 nm (Blue) F>NF
Reversibility	Irreversible	Irreversible	Irreversible	Reversible
Source	Anthozoa-derived (<i>Dendronephthya</i> sp.)	Anthozoa-derived (<i>Trachyphyllia geoffroyi</i>)	Aequorea-derived (<i>Aequorea coerulescens</i>)	Anthozoa-derived <i>Pectiniidae</i> (stony corals)
Reference	(Chudakov et al., 2007)	(Ando et al., 2002)	(Chudakov et al., 2007)	(Andresen et al., 2007)

3.2 Results

3.2.1 Volumetric detection of Purkinje neuron soma using Cellpose

Zebrafish cerebellum has a small population of PNs that can be visualised under the microscope (**Fig. 3.1 A top**). This accessibility allows us to track and study the function of the entire PN population during early larval development. As an important step towards this goal, I optimised Cellpose, a generalist cell segmentation tool ([Stringer et al., 2021](#); [Stringer & Pachitariu, 2024](#)).

I utilised Cellpose for 3D segmentation of PNs tagged fluorescently using Dendra2 that were imaged in alive fish using confocal microscopy. Each cerebellar lobe was imaged with 1µm thin slices and was rescaled to 512 X 384 (X * Y) pixels to have at least ~2500 pixels per soma. To reduce the noise from the neuropil, all images were first restored using the 'denoise_cyto3' model and then segmented using the 'cyto3' model ([Stringer & Pachitariu, 2024](#)). Since the 'cyto3' segmentation model works on generalist algorithms, it was important to recursively identify the segmentation parameters to make it accurate for zebrafish PNs. Anisotropy of 3.2 and a threshold 'equivalent diameter volume' (diameter of

a sphere with the same volume as the identified ROI) was set to 3 μm (roughly half of the PN diameter). The 3D ROIs were thereafter evaluated manually using Cellpose GUI to further eliminate inaccurate ROIs, especially from the neuropil. The final 3D masks detect the PN soma with sufficient accuracy (**Fig. 3.1A bottom, B**)

For this study, hybrid segmentation, combining the generalist 'cyto3' model with manual intervention, was used. We now also have a high-accuracy segmentation that can be used in the future to train a specialist tailored to zebrafish PNs (Pachitariu & Stringer, 2022).

Figure 3.1 Three-dimensional segmentation of fluorescently tagged PNs using Cellpose

A. Top: Maximum intensity projection (MIP) of PN population in the cerebellum of a 4 dpf larva. Expression of Dendra2 in PNs was driven by Ca8-cFos enhancer-promoter. Bottom: MIP of 3D volumetric PN masks identified from the top panel using Cellpose.

B. Single cerebellar plane showing PNs along with the outlines obtained from 3D segmentation.

All scale bars are 20 μm

3.2.2 Cerebellar PN population is dynamic and continuously growing during early development

During early larval development, the zebrafish cerebellum is functional yet constantly changing. PNs undergo synaptic pruning to reach climbing fibre mono-innervation (Chapter 2), growth of dendritic arbour (Sitaraman et al., 2021) and potential changes in parallel fibre synapses from the proliferating granule cell population (Kaslin et al., 2013). I evaluated the proliferation of the PN population during the first two weeks of larval development at 4-5 dpf (early stage), 7-8 dpf (intermediate stage) and 11-15 dpf (late stage) (**Fig. 3.2 A left**). When performing single-plane two-photon calcium imaging from dorsal PNs (Chapter 2), a visible increase in the total number of neurons was observed (**Fig. 3.2 A right**). I asked whether this increase in neuronal numbers is due to proliferation or merely an outcome of migration towards dorsal cerebellar planes. To address this question, the entire PN population expressing a fluorescent reporter was imaged using confocal microscopy. PNs were segmented using Cellpose and a combined total count for both lobes was computed. I observed an increasing trend in total PN count from early to intermediate to late larval stages, suggesting that new-born PNs are constantly being integrated in the cerebellar circuit during this phase of larval development (**Fig. 3.2 B**). A similar increase in PNs from the intermediate to late stage was also seen earlier using parvalbumin staining (Hamling et al., 2015; Kaslin et al., 2013). However, the numbers I see using the Ca8-cFos driven fluorescent expression are much higher. Furthermore, I measured the passive properties of medial PNs, which are largely formed very early in development (discussed later in [section 3.2.5](#)). I saw a significant decrease in the input resistance between the early and late larval stages, with an effect size of 0.49 (**Fig. 3.2 C, D**). Median input capacitance also showed an increasing trend, though statistically non-significant but with a moderate effect size of 0.42 (**Fig. 3.2 C, E**). These findings suggest that alongside the integration of new-born PNs, the intrinsic properties of the existing PNs are also changing, thereby contributing to establishing a functional cerebellar circuit in independently locomoting larvae.

Figure 3.2 The PN population grows in size and is extremely dynamic during early larval development

- A.** Left: Representative image showing the larval stages investigated in this study. The Red dashed box shows the location of the cerebellum in the larval brain. Right: Single cerebellar plane showing an increase in PN density from early (bottom) to late (top) developmental stages. Expression of GCaMP6s in PNs was driven by *aldoca* promoter.
- B.** Total PN count increases over development. Median \pm IQR : 289 ± 46 (early), 392 ± 55 (intermediate), 576 ± 76.5 (late). N = 3, 5, 3 larvae for early, intermediate and late stages, respectively.
- C.** Schematic representing current response of a PN to hyperpolarizing voltage pulses. -80mV pulse was used to compute input resistance (R_{in}) and input capacitance (C_{in}). The area under the curve of capacitive transient (highlighted by the red dashed box) was used to calculate C_{in} . A random 30 ms window of the steady-state response (highlighted by a black dashed box) was used to compute R_{in} .
- D.** R_{in} distribution of PNs over development. A window with no spontaneous synaptic inputs was chosen. Median \pm IQR ($G\Omega$): 1.315 ± 1.077 (early), 1.12 ± 0.553 (late)

(Welch's t-test, $P = 0.028$, Cohen's $d = 0.49$). $N = 40$ and 42 cells (from 34 and 40 larvae) for early and late stages.

- E.** Cin distribution of PNs over development. Median \pm IQR (in pF): 14.371 ± 4.958 (early), 17.26 ± 5.929 (late) (Mann-Whitney U test, $P = 0.068$, Cohen's $d = 0.42$). $N = 40$ and 42 cells (from 34 and 40 larvae) for early and late stages.

Holding potential: -55mV . Colours *green*, *grey* and *purple* represent early (4-5 dpf), intermediate (7-8dpf) and late (11-14 dpf) larval stages, respectively. * $P < 0.05$, ns $P > 0.05$.

3.2.3 Expression of genetically encoded Dendra2 in PN population to study new-born PNs

The evidence of neurogenesis in freely swimming larvae raises interesting questions about the functional integration of new-born PNs in the already existing dynamic cerebellar circuit. So far PN neurogenesis has been minimally studied using BrdU pulse-chase experiments in fixed larval preparation (Kaslin et al., 2013) or by cell counting using fluorescent reporters (Fig. 3.1 B and previously in (Hamling et al., 2015)). To study functional aspects of PN neurogenesis, we needed a way to birthdate and track new-born neurons in awake and behaving larval zebrafish. Towards this goal, I utilised Dendra2, a photo-convertible protein that initially fluoresces green (Dendra2-green) but irreversibly switches to red fluorescence (Dendra2-red) upon UV or blue light irradiation (Fig. 3.3 A).

The Dendra2 coding sequence (693 bp long) was obtained from a mammalian expression vector and cloned in the tol2 zebrafish expression vector pT2KXIG downstream of PN-specific Ca8-cFos minimal enhancer-promoter sequence (See Materials and Methods section 3.4.2). The resulting plasmid was named pT2KXIG-Ca8-cFos-Dendra2 (in short, Ca8-cFos-Dendra2 plasmid) (Fig. 3.3 B). The Ca8-cFos-Dendra2 plasmid was then co-injected with Tol2 transposase mRNA in single-celled embryos for genomic integration (Fig. 3.3 C). The 5'-Ca8-cFos-Dendra2-3' sequence is flanked by the T2 sites which are recognised by the Tol2 transposase protein. The transposase inserts DNA sequences flanked by the T2 sites at random genomic loci. As a result, we can drive the expression of Dendra2 specifically in zebrafish PNs (Fig. 3.3 C). Mosaic expression of Dendra2 was

seen in the PNs of the F0 founder generation (**Fig. 3.3 D left, E**). A successful germline integration resulted in stable transgenic expression of Dendra2 in the entire PN population of the F1 generation fish: Tg(Ca8-cFos-Dendra2); Indian WT (**Fig. 3.3 D middle, F**). F0 generation was also crossed with *nacre*^{-/-} albino fish. Consequently, Tg(Ca8-cFos-Dendra2); *nacre*^{-/-} albino line was parallelly obtained in the F2 generation (**Fig. 3 D right**). Expression of Dendra2 in PNs now enables us to study the functional integration of new-born PNs in the cerebellum of developing larval zebrafish.

Figure 3.3 Generation of a tool to visualise new-born PNs in awake larvae and study their function during development

A. Chromophore site of Dendra2, an irreversible photo-convertible protein. The chromophore consists of a critical histidine residue. Dendra2 naturally exists in an

equilibrium between a non-fluorescent state (neutral chromophore site) and a green-fluorescent state (anionic chromophore site). Exposure to UV (400 nm) or blue (~490 nm) light results in a double C α =C β bond at the histidine residue, switching it to red fluorescence.

- B.** Cloning of Dendra2 in a zebrafish expression vector pT2KXIG. Dendra2 DNA sequence was obtained from pDendra2-N, a mammalian expression vector. It was then cloned downstream of Ca8-cFos minimal enhancer-promoter to drive expression in PNs. The resultant plasmid is referred to as pT2KXIG-Ca8-cFos-Dendra2.
- C.** Schematic showing co-injection of pT2KXIG-Ca8-cFos-Dendra2 plasmid and Tol2 mRNA in embryos at the single-celled stage. Tol2 transposon performs random insertion of the plasmid's T2 flanked sequence into the genome. Microinjection in single-celled embryos results in mosaic expression in PNs.
- D.** Schematic representing Dendra2 transgenic lines created in two different genetic backgrounds: pT2KXIG-Ca8-cFos-Dendra2; Indian WT (pigmented) and pT2KXIG-Ca8-cFos-Dendra2; nacre -/- (non-pigmented)
- E.** Mosaic expression of Dendra2 in PNs of a 4dpf founder fish (F0).
- F.** Stable transgenic expression of Dendra2 in PNs of the F1 generation larva (imaged at 4dpf).

All scale bars are 20 μ m.

3.2.4 Photo-conversion Dendra2 in cerebellar PNs of larval zebrafish

I next utilised the transgenic fish Tg(Ca8-cFos-Dendra2) to photo-convert Dendra2 which is specifically expressed in PNs. The transparent skin and dorsal location of the cerebellar PNs make it easy to irradiate the PNs non-invasively. Since UV light is more efficient than blue light in photo-converting Dendra2 (Chudakov et al., 2007), I used a 405 nm UV laser to irradiate the cerebellum using an upright confocal microscope (**Fig. 3.4 A**). The cerebellum was exposed to 5-7 mW UV light for 10-15 seconds. This was repeated thrice with an interval of ~1 minute to prevent tissue damage. After photo-conversion, both red and green Dendra2 were imaged at different intervals (30 minutes, 10 hrs, 48 hrs or 1 week, as per the experimental requirements) using the same confocal microscope (**Fig. 3.4 A**). To compare PNs before and after photo-conversion, one example fish was used to

focally irradiate the right cerebellar lobe while leaving the left lobe intact (**Fig. 3.4 B, C**). Before photo-conversion, a bright green fluorescent signal was measured in the Dendra2-green channel and the Dendra2-red showed negligible fluorescence (**Fig. 3.4 B, Top**). After 30 minutes of irradiation of the right lobe, an enhanced red signal was seen in the right lobe, while the left lobe remained unchanged (**Fig. 3.4 B, Bottom-right**). I used the ratio of Dendra2-red: Dendra2-green mean intensity in each PN soma to compare the photo-converted PNs (right lobe (R)) from control PNs (left lobe (L)) (**Fig. 3.4 C**). This ratio will be referred to as the RbyG ratio. An arbitrary threshold of 0.25 sufficiently distinguishes photo-converted PNs from non-photo-converted ones (indicated by the red dashed line in **Fig. 3.4 C**).

The RbyG ratio is a measure of the Dendra2-red signal in a Purkinje neuron. Higher the RbyG ratio, higher will be the Dendra2-red signal. PNs which were present in the cerebellum and expressed Dendra2-green at the time of photo-conversion show a high RbyG ratio > 0.25 and therefore can be comfortably designated as early-born neurons. On the other hand, a low RbyG ratio < 0.25 means that the neuron was either not born at the time of UV irradiation or was not photo-converted. Since the whole cerebellum is irradiated, the latter can be ruled out. Consequently, new-born PNs can be identified as those with RbyG ratio < 0.25 .

To track the birth-dated new-born PNs, it is important that the Dendra2-red is stable and persists with good levels of red fluorescence for sufficient amounts of time in the early development. To assess the stability of Dendra2-red protein, I imaged the cerebellum at different time points from the time of photo-conversion. The Dendra2-red signal showed prolonged stability for at least up to one week after the photo-conversion (**Fig. 3.4 D**)

The above findings have now set the stage for the utilisation of Dendra2 to birth-date the new-born neurons using the RbyG ratio and assess the PN neurogenic niches in the cerebellum. It will allow us to study their intrinsic and synaptic properties and sensory-motor function. Furthermore, the automated detection of 3D PN soma using Cellpose as shown and discussed in **Fig. 3.1** has also made this study extremely high throughput.

Figure 3.4 Photo-conversion of genetically encoded Dendra2 in the larval zebrafish PNs

A. Schematic showing photo-conversion of Dendra2 in PNs using 405 nm UV light under a confocal microscope. The cerebellum of agarose-embedded larvae is irradiated with ~7.3 mW UV light for 5-10 seconds (X3 times at an interval of 1 minute) using a 60X water immersion objective. Before photo-conversion, Dendra2 exhibits strong green

fluorescence and negligible red fluorescence. After photo-conversion, the red fluorescence increases many-fold, and the green fluorescence also recovers as more Dendra2-green protein is formed.

- B.** Dendra2-green and Dendra2-red fluorescence in the PNs before (top) and after (bottom) localised UV irradiation of the right cerebellar lobe of a 4dpf larva. 30 minutes after UV exposure, enhanced Dendra2-red fluorescence was seen in the right lobe (bottom right panel) - indicating successful photo-conversion. All images show maximum intensity projection of the PNs. Dashed white line highlights the cerebellum. L and R indicate the left lobe and right cerebellar lobes, respectively.
- C.** The ratio of mean red and green fluorescence intensity in PNs of the left (control) and right (photo-converted) lobes 30 minutes after photo-conversion (from images in B, bottom panels). PN soma were segmented using Cellpose and the resultant 3D masks were used to measure the volumetric mean intensities. This ratio is referred to as the RbyG ratio. The red dashed line indicates the arbitrary threshold of 0.25 that sufficiently distinguishes the photo-converted PNs from the control PNs with minimal error. (Mann-Whitney U test, $P = 1.02e-46$)
- D.** Dendra2-red fluorescence was profiled at 10 hrs (left), 48 hrs (middle) and one week (right) after photo-conversion in three different 15 dpf larvae. This suggests prolonged stability of Dendra2-red for at least one week.

Colours *cyan* and *red* represent Dendra2-green and Dendra2-red, respectively. *** $P < 0.001$. All scale bars are 20 μm .

3.2.5 Birth-dating of PNs in the developing cerebellum using Dendra2

To identify the new-born PNs, the whole cerebellum was irradiated with UV light to tag all existing PNs with Dendra2-red. Thereafter, 10 hours later, the red and green intensities in PNs were measured (**Fig. 3.5 A**). Using Cellpose 3D masks of PNs, the RbyG ratio was calculated for individual PNs. Cells with $RbyG < 0.25$ were confidently identified as new-born (highlighted with yellow outlines in **Fig. 3.5 A**). The new-born cells were largely located in the periphery of the cerebellar lobes in early, intermediate and late larval stages (**Fig. 3.5 B**). In early-stage larvae, 10 hours post photo-conversion, ~23% of the total PNs

were new-born (**Fig. 3.5 C**). This fraction declined over development, agreeing with an increase in the total PN numbers during the same developmental window seen earlier (**Fig. 3.2 B**)

- B.** Z-projection of all PNs' location in three representative fish at early (left), intermediate (middle) and late (right) larval stages. New-born PNs (RbyG < 0.25, indicated in cyan) are largely located at the periphery of the cerebellar lobes.
- C.** The fraction of new-born PNs decreases over development, also evidenced in (B). Median \pm IQR: 0.231 \pm 0.06 (early), 0.065 \pm 0.072 (intermediate) and 0.018 \pm 0.012 (late). Colours *green*, *grey* and *purple* represent early (4-5 dpf), intermediate (7-8dpf) and late (11-14 dpf) larval stages, respectively.

3.2.6 New-born PNs form functional climbing fibre synapses within 20 hours

Once I could identify new-born PNs using RbyG ratios in Tg(Ca8-cFos-Dendra2) larvae, I wanted to ask when these neurons formed functional synaptic contacts. To address this question, I recorded electrical activity from new-born PNs using loose patch electrophysiology (**Fig. 3.6 A**). The spike waveforms and amplitudes from the loose patch recordings allow us to distinguish CF inputs and intrinsic simple spikes. I identified a new-born PN from the confocal image and performed a two-minute-long targeted patch recording after 20 hours of photo-conversion (**Fig. 3.6 B, D, top**). This new-born PN exhibited bursts of electrical activity preceded by CF inputs (**Fig. 3.6 D, bottom**), a classic signature of its integration in the cerebellar circuit. The activity of the new-born PN was very similar to that of an early-born neuron (**Fig. 3.6 C**).

These results suggest that within 20 hours of being born, new-born PNs form functional synaptic connections with climbing fibres and show bursting activity. Since bursts are also driven by inhibitory inputs (Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015), PN-inhibitory interneuron connections are also presumably formed by this time. Going forward, it would be interesting to record electrical activity from new-born PNs at shorter intervals after photo-conversion to understand the timeline of their functional integration and emergent functions.

Figure 3.6 Synaptic connections of new-born PNs are established within 20 hours

- A.** Schematic demonstrating loose patch electrophysiological recordings performed from new-born neurons. New-born PNs are those that are positive for Dendra2-green but lack Dendra2-red.
- B.** Representative image of PNs from a single cerebellar plane of a 7 dpf larva, 10 hours after photo-conversion. Left: Dendra2-green fluorescence, Right: Dendra2-red fluorescence. The white arrow indicates the new-born PN which was targeted for electrical recording.
- C.** Top: An old (control) PN targeted for loose patch recording with a glass patch pipette. Bottom: recording from this PN showing simple spikes (pink dots) and climbing fibre (CF) inputs (black dots).
- D.** Top: A new-born PN (indicated in (B)) targeted for loose patch recording. Bottom: CF inputs and bursts (known to be driven largely by synaptic inputs) from this new-born PN show that synaptic connections are formed within 20 hrs of neuronal birth.

3.3 Discussion

In this study, I have performed birth-dating of new-born PNs and assessed their functional incorporation in the cerebellar circuit using photo-convertible protein Dendra2. I first optimised semi-automatic 3D segmentation for larval zebrafish PNs using Cellpose to count the total PN number in the cerebellum during early development. I observed an increase in PN numbers from 4 dpf to 15 dpf, which confirmed high rates of neurogenesis throughout this developmental window. PN population size grew alongside continuous changes in the properties of the existing early born PNs. To study the new-born neurons in awake larvae, I developed a zebrafish expression vector that drives expression of Dendra2 specifically in PNs using the PN-specific Ca8-cFos minimal enhancer-promoter sequence. This vector was used to create PN-specific transgenic line Tg(Ca8-cFos-Dendra2) in wild-type and albino backgrounds. Thereafter, non-invasive photo-conversion was optimised for PNs and a metric called RbyG ratio was used to distinguish the new-born cells from the early-born ones. I found that the newborn PNs are largely localised to the peripheral regions of the cerebellar lobes with ~25% new PNs added in approximately 10 hours during early stage. The rate of neurogenesis reduces to less than 5% by late larval stages. Furthermore, the new-born neurons get integrated into the cerebellar network within 20 hours of being born and exhibit bursts of activity known to be driven by synaptic inputs.

Going forward, we can perform an experiment to create a temporal profile of network activity in PNs by assessing them within 1-2 hours up to 20 hours of photo-conversion to understand the timeline of the formation of climbing fibre, parallel fibre and other inhibitory synapses. This can be further extended to explore whether newly-born PNs directly establish CF mono-innervation or if they undergo synaptic pruning like early-born PNs (discussed earlier in [Chapter 2](#)). An interesting hypothesis is that, once the CF-PN network is fine-tuned, neurogenesis in intermediate and late larval stages conserves energy and resources by enabling new neurons to become directly mono-innervated, guided by existing cues.

The majority of PN axons project to eurydendroid cells within the cerebellum, referred to as internal axons). A subset of PNs also projects outside the cerebellum to non-eurydendroid cell targets via causal axons ([Knogler et al., 2019](#)). It would be

interesting to find out if these projections originate from new-born PNs guided by axon guidance factors distinct from those in early embryogenesis. We could also assess which bistable states new-born PNs tend to prefer. Lastly, we could also study the sensory-motor function of the new-born PNs with the help of calcium imaging. Since the green and red emission spectra are already occupied by Dendra2-green and Dendra2-red respectively, GCaMP and RCaMP cannot be utilised for measuring calcium activity. Instead, we can use WhaloCaMP, a genetically encoded calcium sensor that can be coupled to rhodamine dyes that fluoresce in the near-infrared range (Farrants et al., 2023). Alternatively, Voltron coupled with near-infrared dyes can also be utilised to study the functions of new-born PNs during cerebellar tasks (Abdelfattah et al., 2019).

In summary, this study allows us to utilise zebrafish to understand the development of the cerebellar circuit after birth, while the animal becomes independent. The dataset generated for volumetric segmentation of zebrafish PN can be further utilised to train a specialist model for making fully automated segmentation algorithms. This will improve the analysis for the experiments proposed above. Lastly, new-born PNs can be in addition to birthdating, Dendra2 can also be used to sparsely label PNs without having to go through the trouble of low throughput sparse labelling via single-cell microinjections.

3.4 Materials and Methods

3.4.1 Common methodology

Biosafety and Ethics, animal maintenance and larval zebrafish preparation for single-cell loose patch electrophysiology from PNs are described earlier in [section 2.4](#).

3.4.2 Cloning of pT2KXIG-Ca8-cFos-Dendra2 plasmid

Dendra2 DNA sequence was amplified from pDendra2-N (# 632545, Clontech Laboratories, Takara Bio Company) using forward primer fDendra2EcorI: 5'CCGGAATTCATGAACACCCCGGGAATTAACCTGATC-3' and reverse primer rDendra2Asc1: 5'-TTGGCGCGCCTTACCACACCTGGCTG-3'. The amplicon was inserted

in the pT2KXIG zebrafish vector using EcoR1 and Asc1 restriction sites at 5' and 3' ends. This plasmid has tol2 sites (T2) that are recognised by Tol2 transposase for random transposition (Urasaki et al., 2006).

3.4.3 Generation of transgenic line expressing Dendra2 in PNs

Single-celled Indian WT Zebrafish embryos were pressure injected with 100 ng/ μ L Tol2 transposase mRNA mixed with 50 ng/ μ L pT2KXIG-Ca8-cFos-Dendra2 plasmid. At 7 dpf, larvae were screened for expression of Dendra2-green. Positive F0 larvae were raised and in-crossed after three months to get PN-specific Dendra2 expression in the F1 generation: Tg(Ca8-cFos-Dendra2); Indian WT. Parallely, F0 fish were also crossed with nacre -/- to generate heterozygous nacre Dendra2 fish. Incrossing these F1 fish gave rise to Tg(Ca8-cFos-Dendra2); nacre-/- resulting in Dendra2 expression in PNs in albino background.

3.4.4 Dendra2 Photo-conversion

Larvae were first embedded in 1% agarose in a dorsal-up configuration. A 405 nm UV laser was used to irradiate the cerebellum of individual larvae using an upright confocal microscope (FV3000, Olympus, Japan). The cerebellum was then exposed to 5-7 mW UV light for 10-15 seconds. This was repeated thrice with an interval of ~1 minute to prevent tissue damage. After photo-conversion, the larvae were released and raised in E3 solution. Thereafter, both red and green Dendra2 were imaged at different intervals (30 minutes or 10 hrs or 48 hrs or 1 weeks, as per the experimental requirements) using the same confocal microscope. Alternatively, bulk photo-conversion can also be performed in freely swimming larvae, using bright UV light for ~5 to 10 minutes.

3.4.5 Confocal imaging of Dendra2-green and Dendra2-red

Dendra2 expression in the PNs was imaged using a 20X or 60X water immersion objective using an upright confocal microscope (FV3000, Olympus, Japan). Dendra2-red and Dendra2-green were imaged in two separate phases using high-sensitivity detectors. Dendra2-green was imaged using a 488 nm laser (2-3% of absolute laser power, measured with 10X objective as 6.3 mW) and emission was collected in the range of 500 -

540 nm. Dendra2-red was imaged using a 561 nm laser (2-3% of absolute laser power, measured at 10X objective as 6.8 mW) and emission was collected from 565 - 665 nm. While blue light (488 nm) can also induce photo-conversion of Dendra2-green to red, the laser power and exposure time needed for this process are significantly higher. Thus, imaging at the current laser power is safe without the risk of photo-conversion.

3.4.6 Analysis and statistics

3D segmentation using Cellpose was performed using a Python script adapted from the authors (Stringer et al., 2021; Stringer & Pachitariu, 2024). All downstream analysis was performed using custom scripts written in Python and Fiji macro.

3.5 Acknowledgments

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Chapter 4: Intrinsic and network properties of PNs in developing cerebellum

The PNs, once born, undergo changes in their intrinsic and synaptic properties as they mature. This includes changes in intrinsic properties (Chapter 3, Fig. 3.2), morphology, activity patterns and formation and careful elimination of chemical and electrical synapses. The expression of gap junction proteins is critical for PNs to form glutamatergic synapses (Sitaraman et al., 2021). Furthermore, the formation of excitatory and inhibitory synapses gives rise to a characteristic bistability in PNs (Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015). Here, we discuss some of these properties of PNs that contribute to shaping their function during early larval development.

4.1 Role of electrical synapses formed by PNs in cerebellar circuit maturation

Electrical synapses play an important role in the assembly of neural circuits during early development. Initially, their expression constantly increases to provide structural support while the chemical synapses are being formed. Subsequently, their expression declines in most brain regions by adulthood (Belluardo et al., 2000). These synapses consist of two hemi-channels that dock at the interface of two neurons. Each hemichannel is a pore-forming hexamer of individual subunits called connexins in vertebrates and innexins in invertebrates. Our work has shown that *Gjd2b* (also known as *Cx35b*) is essential for dendritic growth and proper formation of glutamatergic synapses (Sitaraman et al., 2021). In *gjd2b*^{-/-} larvae, a reduced frequency of miniature currents (mEPSCs) was observed (**Fig. 4.1 A left**). CF-PN synapses are one of the strongest synapses in the brain with a high release probability (P_r) (Silver et al., 1998). We investigated whether the decrease in mEPSC frequency was due to a decrease in P_r at CF-PN synapses. Paired-pulse experiments were conducted to measure neurotransmitter P_r at CF-PN synapses. The *gjd2b* mutants showed comparable release probability to WT larvae (**Fig. 4.1 A centre,**

right). Furthermore, ultrastructure analysis revealed that the reduced mEPSC frequency in mutant PNs was explained by a stunted dendritic arbour with fewer glutamatergic synapses (Sitaraman et al., 2021). Gjd2b expression was rescued in a PN-specific manner using a full-length functional variant or a pore-dead variant lacking N-terminal residues 5 to 21 (**Fig. 4.1 B**). The full-length gjd2b was able to rescue the stunted arbour, whereas the pore-dead variant could not (**Fig. 4.1 C**). These observations suggest that a functional gjd2b mediated pore-forming gap junction is critical for the formation of chemical synapses and the maturation of PN dendritic arbour.

We next evaluated the general occurrence of gap junctions in the larval cerebellum. Towards this, we analysed the existing single-cell RNA sequencing database to examine the expression profiles of various connexins in PNs, granule cells, eurydendroid neurons and inferior olivary nucleus/ CFs (Takeuchi et al., 2017). We saw a large abundance of ten different connexins in cerebellar neurons (**Fig. 4.2 D**). Cx43 and Cx43.4 emerged as the most prevalent connexins in the cerebellum. When gjd2b and Cx43 were co-expressed, we observed partial co-localization in a subset of PNs (**Fig. 4.2 E**). This indicates that gjd2b and Cx43 not only cluster within the same gap junctional plaque but may also form heteromeric hemichannels. Subunit clustering may not only be limited to Cx 43 and gjd2b, but could also involve other connexins that are expressed in PNs. These hemichannels in PNs could dock with other connexins in the cerebellar neurons, potentially facilitating diverse functions.

These findings highlight the possibility of interactions among different gap junction proteins via the clustering of different channel subunits in PNs during early development. Such interactions may play a significant role in the maturation and functional organization of the cerebellum.

Figure 4.1 Cross-talks between electrical and chemical synapses are important for cerebellar maturation

A. Left: Reduced mEPSC frequency in Connexin Cx35/ *gjd2b* mutants. Centre and Right: Paired-pulse experiment to compare the presynaptic release probability in wild-type and Cx35/ *gjd2b* mutants (Sitaraman et al., 2021).

- B.** Cloning of pore-dead variant of *gjd2b* in zebrafish expression vector.
- C.** Pore-dead *gjd2b* could not rescue the stunted dendritic arbour of PNs in *gjd2b* mutants. (Experiment conducted by Sahana Sitaraman (Sitaraman et al., 2021)).
- D.** Expression profile of different connexins in cerebellar cells and inferior olivary neurons (Analysed from (Takeuchi et al., 2017)).
- E.** Co-localization of Cx43-gfp and *gjd2b*-mCherry and eCFP cell-fill in zebrafish PNs. PN-specific co-expression was driven by Ca8-cFos through microinjection in single-cell albino (*nacre*^{-/-}) embryos. Images were captured at 4 dpf using a confocal microscope.

4.2 Intrinsic tonic firing in PNs of developing larval zebrafish

PNs exhibit bistable membrane potential (Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015; Chang et al., 2020; Jadhav et al., 2024). Bistable PNs were initially identified in adult mammalian cerebellar slices (Loewenstein et al., 2005). However, their prevalence under physiological conditions was first studied by [Sengupta & Thirumalai \(2015\)](#) using larval zebrafish. Bistable PNs can be seen very early in zebrafish development (**Fig. 4.2 A, B**). Bistability refers to the ability of PNs to rest at two distinct stable membrane potentials: approximately -45 mV and -65 mV. When resting at a depolarised membrane potential of around -45 mV, PNs exhibit tonic firing of sodium-mediated simple spikes (**Fig. 4.2 A, B left**). In contrast, when hyperpolarized below approximately -60 mV, PNs generate bursts of simple spikes (**Fig. 4.2 A, B right**).

Tonic firing is intrinsic to PNs and occurs even in the absence of synaptic inputs. We assessed the biophysical properties of PNs that could underlie this mode of activity. Zebrafish PNs exhibit large currents mediated by L-type voltage-gated calcium channels upon depolarization (Takeuchi et al., 2017; Jadhav et al., 2024). We tested the role of L-type calcium channels in tonic firing by reversibly blocking them with nifedipine while using synaptic blockers (Fox et al., 1987). PNs were held at a hyperpolarized membrane potential and then briefly depolarized using a square current pulse (**Fig. 4.2 C**). Tonic simple spike firing was evoked when the membrane potential reached close to -45 mV

(**Fig. 4.2 C left**). We saw that the PNs failed to fire tonically when L-type calcium channels were blocked (**Fig. 4.2 C middle, E, F**). Tonic simple spike firing was restored after washing out nifedipine (**Fig. 4.2 C right**), emphasising the contribution of L-type calcium channels. Furthermore, L-type calcium channels maintain tonic simple spike firing in PNs by activating SK channels during the repolarization phase (Jadhav et al., 2024). Blocking L-type channels reduces the activation of SK channels and consequently slows down K⁺ efflux during repolarization. This explains the increase in simple spike threshold and decrease in after-hyperpolarization (AHP) amplitude in the presence of nifedipine (**Fig. 4.2 F, G**). In summary, intrinsic tonic simple spike firing in PNs is sustained by L-type calcium channels by facilitating repolarisation via SK channels.

Figure 4.2 L-type calcium channels maintain tonic simple spike firing in zebrafish PNs

A. Example whole-cell recordings from a tonic (left) and a bursting (right) PN.

B. Same as (A) for a different set of neurons recorded using loose patch electrophysiology.

C. Effect of 200 μM nifedipine (L-type calcium channel blocker) on tonic firing of a representative PN at 6 dpf. Tonic firing is abolished with nifedipine treatment and it recovers a few minutes after wash. In red: 1 second long depolarising current pulse injected to a hyperpolarized PN. This experiment was conducted in the presence of synaptic blockers (NBQX (20 μM) + Gabazine (10 μM)). The colours black and blue indicate recording/ measurements performed in the absence or presence of nifedipine, respectively.

D. Simple spike rate decreases when L-type calcium channels are blocked.

E. Simple spike adaptation ratio increases with nifedipine treatment.

F. Nifedipine causes an increase in spike threshold.

G. AHP amplitude decreases with nifedipine treatment

(D-G: N= 6 cells, analysis performed by Meha Jadhav (Jadhav et al., 2024))

4.3 Switch between PN states is a physiologically relevant phenomenon

Synaptic inputs- both inhibitory and excitatory, are the major contributors of bursts in PNs (Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015). Here, I also observed a very rare occurrence of bursts in PNs when synaptic inputs were blocked (**Fig. 4.3 A**). I first attributed this to the presence of Hyperpolarization-activated cyclic nucleotide-gated (HCN1 and 2) channels in zebrafish PNs (Takeuchi et al., 2017). The role of HCN in inducing bursts is minimal as blocking of HCN channels does not keep the PNs from bursting. Therefore, I focused on the more relevant network-induced bursts to understand the context under which they may arise from network activity.

I asked if environmental cues trigger a switch in the PN state. Towards this, I analysed loose patch recordings from PNs performed during multi-directional 2D open-loop optic flow presentation (see Materials and Methods section 4.5.5). A subset of PNs, which typically fire tonically in the dark, transition to a bursting state when the optic flow is turned on (**Fig. 4.3 B**). In the representative PN (shown in **Fig. 4.3 B**), the recording was initiated

when the larva was in the dark. It exhibited a largely tonic state at this time. Thereafter, the optic flow was presented with a 3 s moving phase (shaded in pink) followed by a 3 s stationary phase. During the optic flow presentation, this PN switched from tonic to bursting state, with bursts highly synchronous with the moving phase of the optic flow. The bursting index (defined as mean inter-spike interval (ISI) divided by median of ISI) also showed a sustained elevation during optic flow presentation. As soon as the flow was turned off and the surroundings reverted to complete darkness, the neuron switched back to the tonic state. This bursting-to-tonic switch was also reflected by an instant drop in the bursting index.

Next, I compared the change in bursting activity of PNs in response to optic flow, at different larval stages. The bursting index was calculated for a 2-minute dark phase before the presentation of the optic flow (pre) and for a 2-minute window at the end of the optic flow (post). 62% of the early-stage PNs showed an increase in the bursting index, whereas only 44% of the late-stage PNs showed an increase in the bursting index (**Fig. 4.3 C**). I also found a small subset of neurons which switched from tonic to bursting state when the larvae began to swim (**Fig. 4.3 D**). These observations suggest that these state switches are physiologically relevant and enable PNs to encode sensory-motor information.

Bursts are also largely preceded by an elevation in CF inputs. Since early-stage PNs are poly-innervated by CFs, pruning of extra fibres could potentially affect their influence on PN state switches. The complex interplay between excitatory and inhibitory inputs and downstream molecular signalling can orchestrate PN state switches (Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015). In summary, PN activity is extremely dynamic and can constantly switch between tonic and bursting states. The switch can be modulated by sensory cues and motor function.

Figure 4.3 PN states switch often during sensory and motor functions

A. Top: A representative PN that showed bursts of activity in external saline. Bottom: Recording from the same PN after treatment with synaptic blockers (NBQX (20 μ M) +

Gabazine (10 μ M)). Bursts disappeared, however, a very rare occurrence of a burst in the absence of synaptic inputs was seen.

- B.** A representative PN that shows bursts of activity synchronised with optic flow. Bursting index was calculated for a 2-minute window in the dark before switching on the optic flow (pre) and the last two minutes of the optic flow (post). Fractions of cells with fold change (post/ pre) greater than one are shown here. N = 37, 37, 34 cells for early, intermediate and late larval stages, respectively.
- C.** Fraction of PNs that showed an increase in their bursting index in response to optic flow, over development.
- D.** PN state switch can also happen at an instance of a motor bout. Whole-cell recording from a tonically firing PN (black) that switched to bursting when the fish executed a motor bout (blue). Dynamic bursting index (grey) is indicated on top of the recording.

4.4 Perturbation of CF pruning

CF inputs are critical to the cerebellar function. The CF-PN synapses undergo synaptic pruning during early larval development, resulting in the refinement of sensory-motor encoding in PNs (Chapter 2). CFs also trigger bursts of simple spikes in PNs. A larger fraction of PNs during early development show an elevated bursting index in response to sensory cues (**Fig. 4.3 C**). Therefore, perturbation of synaptic pruning could provide valuable insights to better understand its role in motor learning, prediction, and its impact on sensory-motor encoding in PNs.

Mammalian studies have identified the importance of postsynaptic metabotropic glutamate receptor (mGluR) signalling and voltage-gated calcium channels in CF-PN pruning using genetic perturbation (Hashimoto et al., 2001, 2011; Kano et al., 2018). *In-vitro* studies have shown that Neuronal Calcium-binding protein 2 (necab2) co-localizes with mGluRs. necab2 and mGluR interact in a calcium-dependent manner (Canela et al., 2009). Co-localization between mGluR and necab2 has also been reported in the zebrafish cerebellum (**Fig. 4.4 A, B**) (Chen et al., 2022). I evaluated the expression of necab2 in cerebellar PNs using parvalbumin immunostaining and found that a large fraction of PNs express the protein (**Fig. 4.4 A**). Based on this information, I hypothesised that necab2 - mGluR signalling is required for synaptic pruning, and the absence of necab2 will perturb

mono-innervation. To test this hypothesis, I evaluated mono-innervation of PNs in *necab2* mutant fish generated by [Chen et al \(2022\)](#), using graded CF stimulation (described in [section 2.4.9](#)) (**Fig. 4.4 B, C**). Homozygous *necab2* mutant larvae did not show any visible defects in CF pruning (**Fig. 4.4 C**). PNs were largely mono-innervated by CFs by the late larval stage (11-14 dpf).

Although *necab2* is strongly expressed in PNs, shows strong co-localization with mGluR1 in zebrafish cerebellum and serves as a potential mediator between mGluRs and voltage-gated calcium channels, it still may not contribute to synapse elimination due to compensatory mechanisms and redundancy.

Although the above genetic approach to perturb CF elimination did not work as expected, alternative methods can be tested in future. Elimination of surplus fibres is a competitive process requiring asynchronous activity. One way to disrupt pruning would be to interfere with this activity-dependent competition. This can be achieved by synchronising the olivary neurons using chemical treatment with harmaline ([Andjus et al., 2003](#)). However, such chemical approaches may produce non-specific effects that are difficult to control. Alternatively, synchronisation of olivary neurons can also be achieved using optogenetics. Towards this goal, I have generated a transgenic zebrafish line that expresses an excitatory opsin CheRiff in the olivary neurons (Hochbaum et al., 2014; Antinucci et al., 2020). Tg(hspGFFDMC28C-Gal4; UAS:CheRiff-tdTomato) were generated by single-cell transgenesis using Tol2-UAS:CheRiff-tdTomato plasmid. Successful germline integration was achieved and CheRiff-tdTomato expression was seen in olivary neurons (**Fig. 4.4 D**). These transgenic larvae can be used to synchronise the inferior olivary neurons by shining blue light periodically during the first two weeks of development.

Identification of a specific approach to perturb CF pruning is still ongoing, and the optogenetic method holds potential as a non-invasive way to achieve this.

Figure 4.4 Perturbation of CF elimination in larval zebrafish

A. Co-localization of necab2 and parvalbumin (PN marker) shown using immunostaining. Scale bars 20 μ m and 5 μ m for left and right, respectively. The white dashed box is zoomed in on the left panel. Arrows indicate the expression of necab2 in PNs.

- B.** Left: Expression of *necab2* in wild-type larval brain. Abundant expression was seen in the cerebellum. Right: *necab2* immunostaining in mutant larvae (Chen et al., 2022).
- C.** Distribution of mono- and poly-innervated PNs in early (left) and late (right) larval stages. Mutants show no visible perturbation of synaptic pruning. Chi-square test ($P = 0.366$ for late stage WT vs *Necab*^{-/-} mutants) $N = 16$, 16 cells (WT) and $N = 17$, 20 cells (*Necab*^{-/-}) for early and late larval stages, respectively. Arrows indicate the cerebellum.
- D.** Expression of *CheRiff* in the inferior olivary neurons of *Tg(hspGFFDMC28C-Gal4; UAS:CheRiff-tdTomato)* transgenic line, generated using Tol2 transposition. Scale bars 20 μm .

4.5 Materials and Methods

4.5.1 Paired-pulse experiment

CFs were stimulated using a custom-made twisted pair bipolar electrode along with simultaneous whole-cell voltage-clamp recordings (described in detail in section 2.4.11). Current intensity that resulted in maximal response with 100% success in all trials was first identified. This intensity was then used to deliver paired current pulses at inter-stimulus intervals ranging from 30 ms to 1 second. The ratio of CF EPSC evoked by the second to first pulse was calculated to get the paired-pulse ratio.

4.5.2 Cloning of pore-dead *gjd2b* in zebrafish expression vector

Gjd2b pore dead sequence was obtained by amplifying the coding sequence while excluding the codons for amino acid residues 5-21. Forward primer FwCX35PD2NcoI : 5'-ACTGCCATGGGGGAATGGATTGGGAGGATCCTGCTAAC-3' and reverse primer rCx35NheI : 5'-TAGCGCTAGCAACGTAGGCAGAGTCACTGG-3' were used. The amplicon was inserted in the zCCM22 zebrafish vector downstream of Ca8-cFos using NcoI and NheI restriction sites at 5' and 3' ends. Pore-dead *gjd2b* was linked to a

C-terminal mCherry tag. The resultant plasmid was identified as zCCM22-Ca8-cFos-Gjd2b^{Δ5-21}.

4.5.3 Co-expression of different connexins in PNs

zCCM22-Ca8-cFos-Gjd2b (Sitaraman et al., 2021), zCCM22-Ca8-cFos-Cx43 (cloned by Atal Vats) and Ca8-cFos-eCFP (cloned by Dilip MV) were coinjected in albino (*nacre*^{-/-}) embryos at single-celled stage. ~30 ng/μL of each plasmid, along with 100 ng/μL Tol2 transposase mRNA was used (Urasaki et al., 2006). Larvae were screened for sparse expression of all three tags in PN. At 4 dpf, the larvae were embedded in 1% low melting agarose and imaging was performed using an upright confocal microscope (FV3000, Olympus, Japan). Image was processed in Fiji.

4.5.4 Blocking L-type calcium channels in the absence of synaptic inputs

A dorsal-up preparation was used for whole-cell recordings from PNs (described in section 2.4.5). PNs were identified from their characteristic bistable nature and the presence of CF inputs. Upon getting a successful whole-cell recording from a PN, the recording chamber was first perfused with synaptic blockers dissolved in external saline: 20 μM NBXQ (HB0442, Hello Bio) and 10 μM gabazine (S106, Sigma Aldrich). Perfusion was performed in voltage-clamp mode. Once the CFs were completely abolished, the recording was switched to current clamp mode and the neuron was hyperpolarized by delivering constant negative current until it stably rested around -70 mV. Short ~250 to 500 ms long current steps were delivered to identify the rheobase. Longer pulses were then delivered at a value that evoked reliable tonic firing. Thereafter, the chamber was perfused with a cocktail of synaptic blockers and 200 μM nifedipine (N7634, Sigma Aldrich). The long current pulse was repeated again. Nifedipine was washed out occasionally to check the restoration of simple spikes.

4.5.5 Multi-directional optic flow presentation

Simultaneous loose-patch recordings were performed from PNs alongside presentation of directional stimulus. Directional optic flow was presented in an open-loop environment

along with simultaneous loose patch recording from PN. The experiment consisted of five blocks of visual stimulus. Each block consisted of eight randomised trials in one of the eight directions, i.e., forward, backwards, left, right, forward left, forward right, backwards left and backwards right. As a result, five trials were presented for each direction. Each trial consisted of a 5 s stationary period followed by a 3 s flow period.

4.5.6 Calculation of rolling window bursting index

To visualise real-time switching in PN states, bursting index (defined as mean inter-spike interval (ISI) divided by median of ISI) was computed for a rolling window. To capture variability in bursts, duration of the window was set individually for each recording to four times the maximum ISI in the recording. Rolling window duration for optic flow induced switch (**Fig. 4.3 B**) and swim induced switch (**Fig. 4.3 D**) was computed as 10 s and 5 s respectively.

4.5.7 Immunostaining

7 dpf Indian wild-type larvae were used for immunostaining of *necab2* and parvalbumin. The larvae were first euthanised in ice-cold tricaine and then fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde dissolved in PBST for 12-14 hours at 4°C. Thereafter, the fixed larvae were washed using PBST and dissected to expose the cerebellum. The gut and tissue around the brain was removed with fine forceps. This was followed by overnight blocking with 5% normal goat serum (005-000-121, Jackson ImmunoResearch). α -parvalbumin (1:2000; raised in mouse, Mab1572, Sigma Aldrich, USA) and α -*necab2* (1:250, raised in rabbit, received from Prof Su Guo, UCSF) were used to label PNs and *necab2*, respectively, for 48 hours at 4°C. This was followed by PBST wash and secondary antibody treatment (1:500) for 12-14 hours at 4°C. The larvae were finally washed with PBS and mounted using ProLong™ Gold Antifade Mountant (P36934, Invitrogen). Each washing step refers to 10 minutes of gentle shaking at 4°C, repeated five times. An inverted confocal microscope (FV3000, Olympus, Japan) was used for imaging.

4.5.8 Generation of transgenic line to express CheRiff in olivary neurons

The tol1 sites in pTol1-UAS:CheRiff-tdTomato plasmid (124234, Addgene) were swapped with tol2 sites to create pTol2-UAS:CheRiff-tdTomato plasmid (cloned by Aalok Varma) (Antinucci et al., 2020; Hochbaum et al., 2014). The Tol2 plasmid was then microinjected in Tg(hspGFFDMC28C-Gal4; UAS:GFP) embryos at single-celled stage. Larvae positive for tdTomato but negative for GFP were screened and raised. The F0 founder population was then in-crossed to get a stable transgenic expression of CheRiff-tdTomato in the inferior olivary neurons. The resultant transgenic line is identified as Tg(hspGFFDMC28C-Gal4; UAS:CheRiff-tdTomato).

Chapter 5: Concluding remarks and discussion

The cerebellum undergoes massive reorganisation during early postnatal development. In this thesis, I have studied diverse questions on the development of cerebellar PN function via a combination of genetics, *in vivo* electrophysiology, ion channel biophysics, and two-photon and light-sheet calcium imaging. I have addressed three aspects of sculpting the cerebellar circuit during early development using larval zebrafish. These include a) Functional implications of climbing Fiber (CF) - Purkinje neuron (PN) synaptic pruning (Chapter 2), b) PN neurogenesis during early cerebellar development (Chapter 3) and, c) Changes in intrinsic and network properties of PNs during early development (Chapter 4).

5.1 Functional implications of CF-PN synaptic pruning

Roughly 40-50% of all synapses formed during embryonic and early postnatal development are lost before maturity (Huttenlocher & Dabholkar, 1997). How this drastic process affects circuit function remains less explored. In the mammalian cerebellum, Purkinje neurons (PNs) receive multiple CF innervations (poly-innervation) at birth. In the first month of postnatal development, surplus CFs are eliminated, leaving only a single fibre (mono-innervation). Over the past few decades, extensive studies have been performed to understand the molecular and cellular processes that orchestrate CF pruning (reviewed by (Kano et al., 2018)). But, very little was known so far about its functional implications. I set out to address this question using larval zebrafish, which hatch early and exhibit independent motor function involving the cerebellum, even before the cerebellum matures. Simultaneous CF stimulation and PN whole-cell recordings revealed that PNs are largely poly-innervated at the early larval stage and attain mono-innervation by two weeks post-fertilisation. The trend is consistent with signatures of pruning seen in a previous study at early and intermediate stages (Hsieh et al., 2014). However, poly-innervated PNs show only three fibres at most, which could be an underestimate caused by single-point stimulation of CFs at the site of entry in the cerebellum. A more accurate innervation index can perhaps be obtained by optogenetic stimulation of the inferior olivary neurons or CFs

using transgenic fish Tg(hspGFFDMC28C-Gal4; UAS:CheRiff-tdTomato) (described in section 4.4). Similar to electrical stimulation, CFs can be optically stimulated at their point of entry in the cerebellum. Alternatively, spatially resolved stimulation of individual IO neurons can be performed using patterned optogenetics. In this experiment, whole-cell voltage-clamp recording from a single PN can be coupled to systematic optic stimulation of all 80-100 IO neurons, one at a time. Since the inferior olivary neurons are electrically coupled, this experiment must be performed in the presence of gap junction blockers (Condorelli et al., 2000; Takeuchi et al., 2017). This method will also give us a spatial map of IO projection to PN over development. Furthermore, anatomical assessment of CF innervation can be performed using retrograde tracers like cholera toxin. Fluorescent cholera toxin can be introduced in PNs using single cell electroporation and individual IO that take up the toxin can be identified as their synaptic partners.

After establishing the timeline of CF pruning, I asked how pruning affects cerebellar function. Using 2D, open loop fictive optomotor behaviour and patch-clamp recordings, I induced a mismatch between motor execution and visual assessment. CFs bring error or teaching signals to the PNs and are expected to occur at swim initiation in the absence of sensory-motor feedback (Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015). Early-stage poly-innervated PNs receive multiple CF inputs of varying strengths. The strong inputs were temporally locked to swim starts, but weak inputs showed poor temporal precision. On the contrary, in late-stage mono-innervated PNs with a single dominant fibre, a very high temporal precision was seen. This suggests that CF pruning reduces noise from multiple weak inputs, and thereby improves the salience of the CF error signal. Furthermore, the timing of CF input is extremely critical for cerebellar plasticity. CF inputs occurring within 120 ms of parallel fibre (PF) inputs reliably induce long-term depression (LTD) or long-term potentiation (LTP) at PF-PN synapses (Albus, 1971; Ito & Kano, 1982; Marr, 1969; Suvrathan et al., 2016). Therefore, by reducing the CF noise, pruning could also pave the way for cerebellar plasticity and learning. In addition to motor error, CF inputs also carry indirect direction-selective visual inputs. I observed that late-stage PNs receive directionally tuned CF inputs, while early-stage PNs receive multi-directional inputs due to the convergence of multiple fibres. As CF inputs drive PN activity, late-stage PNs show a higher level of direction selectivity compared to early-stage PNs. This suggests that the PN population becomes more specialised as mono-innervation progresses. The functional specialization is also reflected in the high level of asynchrony observed when PN activity was measured using calcium imaging. A previous study from our lab has shown that CF

inputs mediate prediction and prediction error signals in PNs when repetitive visual stimuli are presented (Narayanan et al., 2024). Combining 2-photon calcium imaging of PN activity with optomotor behaviour, I found an enhanced sensory-motor error fidelity in stages where PNs are mono-innervated. In summary, this part of the thesis suggests that during the first two weeks of larval development, CF pruning fine tunes sensory and error encoding and paves the way for a functional cerebellar function and behaviour.

5.2 Perturbation of CF-PN synaptic pruning

The metabotropic glutamate receptor (mGluR) signalling pathway along with voltage-gated calcium channels in postsynaptic PNs are extremely critical for CF pruning (Hashimoto et al., 2001, 2011; Kano et al., 2018). I attempted to perturb the elimination of supernumerary CF inputs by utilizing zebrafish mutants of Neuronal Calcium Binding 2 (*necab2*), a protein that interacts with mGluRs in a calcium-dependent manner (Canela et al., 2009). However, CF innervation appeared largely unaffected in *necab2* knock-out larvae, potentially due to compensatory mechanisms and/ or functional redundancy.

Microglia proliferation is another potential candidate that can be used for perturbation of CF pruning. Microglia uniquely enhance GABAergic inhibition in the cerebellum and are implicated in the elimination of excess fibres (Nakayama et al., 2018). Going forward, depletion of microglial proliferation can be opted as an alternative approach to perturb CF pruning. In zebrafish, Pexidartinib (PLX3397) has been previously utilised to delete microglia (Conedera et al., 2019). A more cell-specific and non-toxic approach to perturbing CF elimination could involve disrupting the activity-dependent competition between individual fibres. According to the punishment-protection model of synaptic pruning (discussed in Chapter 1), asynchronous activity between competing synaptic partners results in a local protection signal and a diffusible punishment signal. As a consequence, the maximally active fibre emerges as a winner. We can leverage the transparent nature of zebrafish to non-invasively synchronise inferior olivary neurons using optogenetics. To achieve this, a transgenic zebrafish line Tg(*hspGFFDMC28C-Gal4*; UAS:CheRiff-tdTomato) (discussed in Chapter 4) which expresses an excitatory opsin CheRiff in inferior olivary neurons can be used (Hochbaum et al., 2014; Antinucci et al., 2020). The inferior olivary neurons can be synchronised by exposing the larvae to blue light either periodically or continuously during development. We expect that

synchronisation will interfere with the activity-dependent competition and that persistent poly-innervation is likely to occur, as multiple fibres may fail to be selectively eliminated.

Implementation of a selective and non-invasive perturbation of CF pruning, as suggested above, could provide valuable insights into its impact on motor behaviour which is otherwise challenging to address due to complex developmental dynamics.

5.3 Intrinsic and network properties of PNs over development

As early as 4 dpf, PNs fire simple spikes both tonically and in bursts (Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015). Tonic firing is intrinsic and is sustained by L-type calcium channels that facilitate membrane repolarization after a spike by activating SK channels (Jadhav et al., 2024).

The synaptic connections (formed with the help of by gap junctions), allow bursts of activity in PNs (Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015; Sitaraman et al., 2021). In response to sensory-motor cues, PNs can toggle between the intrinsic tonic state and a network induced bursting state. This is also evidenced by an increase in CF frequency at burst starts (Sengupta & Thirumalai, 2015). Therefore, pruning of CF-PN synapses can potentially refine the PN response to physiologically relevant stimuli by enabling them to tune in or out of the network activity.

5.4 PN neurogenesis during cerebellar development

The continued development of the zebrafish cerebellum while the larvae begin to exhibit independent motor functions, allows investigation of cerebellar maturation in parallel with behavior. I optimised a semi-automated pipeline in Cellpose for 3D segmentation of zebrafish PNs (Stringer et al., 2021). Consistent with previous studies, I found an increase in total PN numbers between early and late larval stages (Hamling et al., 2015; Kaslin et al., 2013). Thereafter, I developed a transgenic line expressing Dendra2 specifically in Purkinje neurons. Dendra2 is a photoconvertible protein that irreversibly changes from

green to red fluorescence upon exposure to UV (or blue) light. This PN-specific Dendra2 transgenic line was used to birth-date PNs non-invasively by exposing the larvae to UV light. The photo-converted red form of Dendra2 was found to be very stable and therefore could allow us to track the new-born PNs for at least one week. Based on the intensity of the red and green form of Dendra2, I have suggested a metric RbyG ratio as a reliable identifier of a PN as new-born or early-born, with reference to the time of photo-conversion. I found that the rate of neurogenesis is highest at the early stage. When tracked after 10 hours of birthdating, I found that ~20% of the total population is newly born. The percentage decreases to less than 5% in the late stage. Neurogenesis was also largely restricted to the periphery of the cerebellar lobes. Within 20 hours of being born, the PNs formed functional CF synapses. They also showed bursts of activity involving inhibitory inputs. Going forward, with the help of this transgenic tool and the observations I have made so far, we can study the functional incorporation of new-born PNs and understand the assembly of the evolutionarily conserved cerebellar architecture.

Appendix: Plasmids and transgenic lines generated

List of transgenic lines		
Transgenic line	Method	Description
Tg(Ca8-cfos-eGFP)	Microinjected Ca8-cfos-eGFP plasmid and Tol2 mRNA in single celled Indian WT embryos	Expresses eCFP in Purkinje neurons of Indian WT fish
Tg(Ca8-cFos-Dendra2); Indian WT	Microinjected pT2KXIG-Ca8-cFos-Dendra2 plasmid with Tol2 mRNA in single celled Indian WT embryos	Expresses Dendra2 in Purkinje neurons of Indian WT fish
Tg(Ca8-cFos-Dendra2); nacre ^{-/-}	Crossed Tg(Ca8-cFos-Dendra2); Indian WT <u>with</u> nacre ^{-/-} fish followed by incross of the progeny	Expresses Dendra2 in Purkinje neurons of nacre ^{-/-} fish
Tg(hspGFFDMC28C-Gal4; UAS:CheRiff-tdTomato)	Microinjected pTol2-UAS:CheRiff-tdTomato plasmid with Tol2 mRNA in single celled embryos from Tg(hspGFFDMC28C-Gal4) fish	Expresses excitatory opsin CheRiff In Tg(hspGFFDMC28C-Gal4) line (Hochbaum et al., 2014; Antinucci et al., 2020)
Tg(hspGFFDMC28C-Gal4; UAS:GFP); nacre ^{-/-}	Crossed Tg(hspGFFDMC28C-Gal4; UAS:GFP); nacre^{+/+} <u>with</u> nacre ^{-/-} fish followed by incross of the progeny	Expresses GFP in inferior olivary neurons of albino fish. Generated for live imaging of climbing fibers
Tg(hspGFFDMC28C-Gal4; UAS:GFP, UAS:mcherry); nacre ^{-/-}	Microinjected UAS-mCherry plasmid with Tol2 mRNA in single celled embryos from Tg(hspGFFDMC28C-Gal4; UAS:GFP); nacre^{-/-} fish	Inferior olivary neurons double labelled with GFP and mCherry.

List of plasmids		
Plasmid	Resistance marker	Description
zCCM22-Ca8-cFos-Gjd2b ^{Δ5-21}	Kanamycin	For Purkinje neuron specific expression of pore dead variant of gap junction protein Gjd2b. This variant lacks the N-terminal amino acid residues 5 - 21 that are essential for formation of the gap junction pore.
pT2KXIG-Ca8-cFos-Dendra2	Ampicillin	For Purkinje neuron specific expression of Dendra2 photo-convertible protein
pT2KXIG-Ca8-cFos-Necab2_001	Ampicillin	For Purkinje neuron specific expression of necab2_001

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